

D4.3 Analysis of existing research data cataloguing efforts towards integrated discovery

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Abstract:

This deliverable seeks to review the existing research data cataloguing efforts across the Research Infrastructures, concentrating on those RIs in the five Cluster project: [ENVRI-FAIR](#) for environmental research; [PaNOSC](#) for photon and neutron open science; [ESCAPE](#) for astronomy and particle physics; [SSHOC](#) for social sciences and humanities and [EOSC-Life](#) for biomedicine and life science. We describe metadata standards for cataloguing, catalogue and repository distinctions and approaches to cataloguing drawing upon examples from the Clusters. A brief catalogue status is given for each Cluster, highlighting the strategy adopted with those communities. We conclude with pointers to overarching trends and concerns within the Clusters that the EOSC Portal will need to address; the ultimate goal of this task is to encourage cross-RI adoption of common metadata interoperability guidelines. These guidelines should leverage existing OpenAIRE guidelines for content providers, as well as being congruent with community standards and practices (eg. schema.org and EDM1). This report is based upon the outputs of three collaborative workshops and some detailed desk-based research.

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Disclaimer

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Table of Contents

Executive Summary	5
1. Introduction	7
2. Metadata standards for cataloguing	8
2.1 Catalogue and repository distinctions	8
2.1.1 Data Catalogue, Registry, Directory, Metadata Catalogue	9
2.1.2 Data Repository	10
2.1.3 Catalogue of metadata standards, data models and definitions.	10
2.1.4 Catalogue of catalogues and repositories.	11
2.2 Categories and scope of cataloguing metadata	11
2.2.1. Metadata properties	11
2.2.2. Metadata forms	12
2.2.3. Metadata scope/level and catalogue structures	13
2.3 Generic and specific metadata standards	15
2.3.1 Data type and domain specific standards	15
2.3.2 Generic metadata standards	16
1. OpenAIRE-Guidelines for Data Archives	17
2. DCAT	17
3. Schema.org	18
4. Bioschemas	19
5. DataCite	20
6. EDMII (EOSC Datasets Minimum Information)	20
7. DDI-CDI: Cross Domain Integration	21
2.4 FAIR Catalogues	21
2.5 Cataloging Research Objects other than data	25
3. Disciplinary metadata cataloguing across EOSC Enhance partner RIs and clusters	27
3.1 Approaches to Cataloguing	28
3.1.1 Primary vs Secondary (Derived) Data	28
3.1.2 Catalogue scope	28
3.1.3 Governance of catalogue: policy and authority for governance and catalogue recommendation	29
3.1.4 Access control: open vs highly managed control	30

3.1.5 Degree of curation of content and collections	30
3.1.6 Architecture: Centralised, federated, decentralised	31
3.1.7 Ingest and harmonisation pipelines	32
3.1.8 Exemplar strategies for submission pipelines	33
3.2 Access properties of catalogues	34
3.3. Catalogue users	34
3.4 Access, export and exchange formats and protocols	35
4. The RI Clusters	36
4.1 ENVRI-FAIR	36
4.2 PaNOSC	37
4.3 ESCAPE	37
4.4 SSHOC	38
4.5 EOSC-Life	39
5. Conclusion	43
6. Bibliography	45
7. Appendix A: Cataloging Standards	47

Executive Summary

Task 4 is focussed on aligning the research data cataloguing efforts in the 5 RI Cluster projects - [ENVRI-FAIR](#) for environmental research; [PaNOSC](#) for photon and neutron open science; [ESCAPE](#) for astronomy and particle physics; [SSHOC](#) for social sciences and humanities and [EOSC-Life](#) for biomedicine and life science - with the EOSC Portal. We discuss key topics concerning what is a dataset and a catalogue, metadata standards for cataloguing, metadata catalogue integration and data cataloging strategies, and common themes from the Cluster projects. We also briefly summarize the current status of the Cluster projects cataloging activities. The ultimate goal of this task is to encourage cross-RI adoption of common metadata interoperability guidelines. These guidelines should leverage existing OpenAIRE guidelines for content providers, as well as being congruent with community standards and practices (eg. schema.org and EDM1). This report is based upon the outputs of three collaborative workshops and some detailed desk-based research.

The key point is that *one size does not fit all*.

The Clusters are not homogeneous entities. They are made up of multiple and diverse Research Infrastructures that vary in their cataloguing maturity and approaches. Some have Cluster-wide recommendations and governance but others are so diverse that they delegate to their partner RIs. Data catalogues are governed at: the Cluster, the RI, the RI national/institutional member and the individual resources level. A few Clusters have made steps towards defining their recommendations for FAIR catalogues but most have not.

The diversity of Cluster data ranges over: the data types, the granularity of the data (from structures at atomic resolution to population level data), the necessary associated metadata, the complexity of data and relationships between data sets, data scales (boutique small data resources to large enterprise repositories), and the data objects catalogued (software, tools, workflows, teaching materials).

The definition of what a dataset is is not simple. Each RI has its own thoughts. Metadata is often stratified into data catalogue, dataset and data record, which effects the standards used at each layer, the level of "FAIR compliance" that the catalogue can state a claim to, the depth of cross disciplinary catalogue integration and discoverability and the properties that are relevant to EOSC services. *Similar and/or domain agnostic metadata properties* are used to describe data catalogues and datasets across different scientific domains, typically with shallow level of detail; and *domain-specific metadata properties* related to the nature of the entity are described within data records, typically with deeper level of detail.

All clusters are concerned with *common interfaces and community standards* to operate within a federation of catalogues. They recommend common standards for (low-level) interoperability/discoverability and domain-specific standards (for expressivity and deep interoperability/reuse). Catalogue and metadata harmonisation already exists, and is well established within the thematic communities and should be honoured and respected. Interoperability for its own sake is unproductive and wasteful; the clusters expend effort on interoperability between metadata and their catalogues only where and when it makes sense (through real examples) and brings benefit. The case for arbitrary pan-discipline interoperability of significantly different datatypes is particularly unclear for the Cluster with long-held and diverse RIs where such interoperability may be worth considering *only* where a tangible Use Case is presented.

The Clusters have a spectrum of maturity for their cataloguing activities, web services, portals, dataset dumps and workflow services. However, all have a **significant legacy** of pre-existing categories, repositories and associated processes with different user groups of data generators, data browsers and downloaders, data analysts, and data owners. EOSC should build on what is already used, not force a new manner of working. There is a need to ensure low barriers to entry for portal submission and discovery with maximum convenience for users and providers. Automation is needed where possible to reduce the human work of cataloguing and curation. All report the need to clarify incentives for opening data and reciprocity for doing so. All integrate knowledge and training with services and data, with most providing some support for software and training catalogues.

Not all data is open. The Clusters have a range of access protocols to the data – embargoes, sensitive data, IPR issues etc – and rules of participation. Closed data has limited exposure of metadata and additional metadata for controlling access.

Cluster level catalogues vs RI level catalogues. Some clusters have attempted a single catalogue. Others recognise the heterogeneity and autonomy of their member RIs and seek to overcome the differences through mechanisms other than a single catalogue, through interoperability and federation with standards, APIs and federated custom search. All are concerned with the long term maintenance and sustainability of cluster level catalogues. Lightweight approaches for cross-walking between catalogues and for FAIR cataloguing are favoured by the Clusters with large numbers of RIs and diverse data.

The SSHOC uses the term “Marketplace” but others consider that they do not operate in a marketplace for trading data but instead are enabling access to data. Terminology does matter.

There are a large number of players active in this arena, and a collaborative approach will more likely ensure a more diverse set of adopters of emergent strategy: CODATA, RDA, GOFAIR and especially the FAIRsFAIR project have produced a number of deliverables of relevance, discussed above.

1. Introduction

Task 4 is focussed on aligning the **research data cataloguing** efforts in the 5 RI cluster projects and their constituent content providers with the EOSC Portal, and to foster interoperability for discovery, accessibility and reusability of data.

The goal of this task is to facilitate cross-discovery by encouraging the adoption by the RIs of common metadata interoperability guidelines with the existing OpenAIRE guidelines for content providers, and with standards from community practices (e.g. schema.org, ECDI). The ultimate objective is to integrate the pre-existing and ongoing RI data catalogues into the [OpenAIRE Research Graph](#), whose [APIs](#) will in turn be integrated into the EOSC Portal to provide EOSC scientific product catalogue's functionality.

This deliverable seeks to review the existing research data cataloguing efforts across the Research Infrastructures, concentrating in those RIs in the five cluster projects¹:

- [ENVRI-FAIR](#)² for environmental research
- [PaNOSC](#)³ for photon and neutron open science
- [ESCAPE](#)⁴ for astronomy and particle physics
- [SSHOC](#)⁵ for social sciences and humanities
- [EOSC-Life](#)⁶ for biomedicine and life sciences

We open with a discussion of key topics concerning metadata catalogue integration, data cataloguing strategies and common themes emerging from the Cluster projects. We report on the metadata standards used, and the strategies to collect metadata, and the means by which metadata is exposed. We highlight domain independent metadata standards and APIs, and the extent to which each is already aware of and compliant with the existing [OpenAIRE guidelines](#) for content providers. Where appropriate we refer other significant research data cataloguing efforts in EOSC related projects, covering those dedicated to FAIR (FAIRsFAIR⁷, GO-FAIR⁸) and new RIs that are not represented in the clusters (DISSCo⁹ and IBISBA¹⁰).

Several workshops provided contributions to the report.

FAIRsFAIR project is covering similar ground in parallel, producing a number of deliverables, notably “D2.1 Report on FAIR requirements for persistence and interoperability” (Lehväslaihi *et al.*, 2019), “D2.2 FAIR Semantics: First recommendations” (Le Franc *et al.*, 2020), “D2.3 Set of FAIR data repositories features” (Behnke *et al.*, 2020) and “D2.4 2nd Report on FAIR requirements for persistence and interoperability” (Riungu-Kalliosaari *et al.*, 2020). More recently, FAIRsFAIR invited the authors of this report to participate, along with representatives of the cluster projects, in a [\(Virtual\) Workshop on Metadata catalogues](#)

¹ <https://www.eosc-portal.eu/news/five-new-esfri-cluster-projects-eosc-panorama>

² <https://envri.eu/>

³ <https://www.panosoc.eu/>

⁴ <https://projectescape.eu/>

⁵ <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/>

⁶ <https://www.eosc-life.eu/>

⁷ <https://www.fairsfair.eu/>

⁸ <https://www.go-fair.org/>

⁹ <https://www.dissco.eu/>

¹⁰ <https://www.ibisba.eu/>

[integration for Interdisciplinary Research](#) held on 11 Sept 2020. We are proud to work with FAIRsFAIR and gratefully acknowledge their significant contributions and cooperations.

On 16 November 2020 the session the EOSCHub virtual conference¹¹ ran a session “Thematic Discovery Marketplaces for the European Open Science Cloud - The EOSC ecosystem of open science marketplaces - from EOSC hub to EOSC Future” where all the clusters spoke about their catalogues.

Prior to EOSC-Enhance the EOSCpilot project ran a number of workshops on FAIR data catalogues (notably [How FAIR Friendly is your data catalogue? Exposing FAIR data in EOSC](#)¹²), and proposed the [EDMI](#) (EOSC Datasets Minimum Information), a minimum information metadata guideline to help users and services to find and access datasets reusing existing data models and interfaces. This work is also discussed in this report.

2. Metadata standards for cataloguing

Research data are held in individual resources (repositories), sometimes uniquely but often duplicated, hosted by a variety of institutions and through numerous infrastructures. Each discipline has its own subject-based resources, registries and catalogues, and its own methodologies, practices and standards. Typically the disciplines operate in silos - cataloguing within a silo often presumes context for interpretation and access protocols.

Metadata describe the content, context and provenance of datasets in a standardised and structured manner. The purpose, origin, temporal characteristics, geographic location, authorship, access conditions and terms of use of a dataset are commonly covered properties. The intent of metadata is to provide structured searchable information so that users and tools can find existing data resources and provide a mechanism for citing data. Metadata also enables users to judge whether a particular dataset is suitable for their particular research purpose.

Metadata standards are typically schemas developed by a particular user community, through consensus, to describe a resource type. Canonical specifications undergo a review, maintenance and publishing process and are shared in a public place, for example the [FAIRsharing registry](#).

The EOSC Clusters highlight a number of recurring issues with respect to metadata standards:

- distinctions between metadata catalogues, data catalogues and data repositories;
- distinctions between properties, forms and scope of metadata, notably distinguishing metadata about datasets, metadata about the data within the dataset and metadata about the catalogue itself;
- the use of data and domain specific standards and generic standards
- the application of FAIR principles to catalogues and what defines a “FAIR catalogue”;

Each cluster has its own terminology which adds to communication complexity.

2.1 Catalogue and repository distinctions

¹¹ <https://realising-eosc.eosc-hub.eu/>

¹² <http://tinyurl.com/osf-eosc-datacat>, <http://tinyurl.com/osf-eosc-datacat-materials>

The focus of this deliverable is **research data cataloguing**. To scope the review we need to distinguish between data catalogues and repositories, and the metadata used for cataloguing data vs the metadata used for recording data. This is a grey area. The terms “registry” and “catalogue” are often used interchangeably. Key distinctions lie in where the data resides, and, to some extent, the anticipated homogeneity of the content. A catalogue has metadata about its entries (which is not clearcut) and the aspiration to be comprehensive in its inventory. The easiest way a resource acquires the distinction of being a catalogue is through its properties and functions - this is the “duck” test of abductive reasoning¹³. If it quacks like a duck and waddles like a duck, it’s a duck.

What is meant by “metadata catalogue” is another area of terminological contention. Eva Rodriguez from the FAIRsFAIR EU project argues that “a cataloguing effort results in a “metadata catalogue”.

We propose the following distinctions.

2.1.1 Data Catalogue, Registry, Directory, Metadata Catalogue

An inventory, a catalogue of the metadata about a digital object collection that references the content of those objects - a searchable resource that might or might not include the data as such. [Gartner Research](#) proposes that “A data catalogue creates and maintains an *inventory of data assets* through the discovery, description and organization of distributed datasets”.

For a catalogue you look up an entry and go to (resolve) the entry. It gives a community-recognized identifier to its entries and has metadata about the entry. The data itself may be stored internally within the catalogue, or alternatively may be accessed by the metadata stored in the catalogue, which would resolve to an external resource/repository.

The data catalogue provides context to enable data stewards, data/business analysts, data engineers, data scientists and other data consumers to find and understand relevant datasets for the purpose of extracting business or scientific value. These datasets may be held elsewhere in data repositories. Context is provided by metadata in one place. Functions include: metadata discovery, ingestion, translation (mapping), enrichment and the creation of semantic relationships between metadata. These catalogues may well have heterogeneous content.

Examples of catalogues include:

- **EOSC-Life:** The ECRIN Clinical Research Metadata Repository¹⁴ for clinical trials, the BBMRI-ERIC Sample Directory¹⁵; the WorkflowHub¹⁶ for computational workflows; and the FAIRSharing EOSC-Life collection¹⁷ which lightly catalogues over 100 other catalogues/repositories from the RIs.
- **SHHOC:** Service Catalogue¹⁸ and an in pilot Marketplace¹⁹ single point for datasets, tools, training and workflows across all RIs.

¹³ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Duck_test

¹⁴ <https://ecrin.org/tools/clinical-research-metadata-repository>

¹⁵ <https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/>

¹⁶ <https://workflowhub.eu/>

¹⁷ <https://fairsharing.org/collection/EOSCLife>

¹⁸ <https://sshopencloud.eu/service-catalogue>

¹⁹ <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/>

- **PaNOSC**: a planned federated dataset catalogue²⁰ using a federated search engine compatible with OpenAIRE to federate the datasets in the RIs; and a single software catalogue²¹ linked to the analysis and simulation software used in PaN facilities.
- **ESCAPE**: the International Virtual Observatory Alliance IVOA Registry of Registries²²
- **ENVRI-FAIR**: the SeaDataNet Metadata Catalogues²³ and a planned federated single catalogue^{24,25}.

2.1.2 Data Repository

Data Repository is defined by the RDA as a “searchable and queryable interfacing entity that can *store*, manage, maintain and curate Data/Digital Objects”.

You deposit data into a repository and the entry is stored. It gives a community-recognized identifier to its entries and has metadata about the entry.

A data repository provides a service for humans and machines to make data discoverable/searchable through the collection(s) of metadata.²⁶ The NLM defines it as “a place that *holds data*, makes data available to use, and *organizes data in a logical manner*. A data repository may also be defined as an appropriate, subject-specific location where researchers can submit their data. Data repositories may have specific requirements concerning subject or research domain; data re-use and access; file format and data structure; and the types of metadata that can be used. Many data repositories have restrictions on who can deposit data into them based on funding, academic qualification, and quality of data. A number of data repositories that are classified as “open”; and as a result are essentially open to receiving data from anyone. Institutional repositories may accept data or an institution may have a separate data repository” [[National Library of Medicine](#)]. A data repository will use data cataloging metadata standards and its contents still need to be ordered.

Examples of repositories include

- **EOSC-Life**: The ELIXIR Core Data Resources and Deposition Databases²⁷
- **ESCAPE**: Data Infrastructure for Open Science (DIOS)²⁸ which is a federated data infrastructure cloud of data services that forms a data lake.
- **ENVRI-FAIR**: DEIMS-SDR²⁹ (Dynamic Ecological Information Management System - Site and dataset registry) which actually seems to be a repository.

2.1.3 Catalogue of metadata standards, data models and definitions.

The Health Data Research UK HDR-UK³⁰ describe their [metadata catalogue](#) as “a toolkit for creating, sharing,

²⁰ <https://www.panosc.eu/services/data-catalogue/>

²¹ <https://software.pan-data.eu/>

²² <http://rofr.ivoa.net/>

²³ <https://www.seadatanet.org/Metadata>

²⁴ <https://envri.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/Data-Cataloguing.pdf>

²⁵ <https://envri.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/MS18-WP5-Design-of-the-service-catalogue-1.pdf>

²⁶ <https://smw-rda.esc.rzg.mpg.de/index.php/Repository>

²⁷ <https://elixir-europe.org/platforms/data>

²⁸ <https://projectescape.eu/services/data-infrastructure-open-science>

²⁹ <https://deims.org/>

³⁰ <https://www.hdruk.ac.uk/>

and updating data models”. A number of resources act as registries for metadata standards, policies and datasets for cataloguing with communities.

An example is the [FAIRsharing Information Resource](#) (Sansone *et al.*, 2019), which is a recognised resource of EOSC and the RDA, and is used by a number of Clusters, including EOSC-Life and ESCAPE. FAIRsharing is a metadata catalogue that is “a curated, informative and educational resource on data and metadata standards, inter-related to *databases* and data *policies*.” FAIRsharing is a manually curated community resource, collecting information on the data and metadata standards used across a variety of data resources and disciplines. This includes a description of individual standards, vocabularies, reporting guidelines, as well as policies. FAIRsharing is a rich source of information on community resources, providing information at the level of the individual database, exposing information on APIs to access that particular database, and where the data can be downloaded. Most of the metadata standards referred to in this report are registered in FAIRsharing, and many are organized into collections for the domain specific standard group responsible for their oversight. For example, for the ESCAPE Cluster, the International Virtual Observatory Alliance which oversees standardization of data and metadata, standardization of data exchange methods, and keeps a registry of available services for the astronomy community has organised their standards into a FAIRsharing collection³¹.

2.1.4 Catalogue of catalogues and repositories.

A special class of catalogue whose entries are catalogues and data repositories (not datasets). Examples include FAIRsharing, which includes data repositories linked to the standards that they comply with, [re3data.org](#) a registry of research data repositories, and Identifiers.org, which is a registry of (largely) Life Science repositories.

Funder organisations, publishers and Research Infrastructures recommend repositories using these catalogues of repository entries, for example, Nature^{32,33}.

2.2 Categories and scope of cataloguing metadata

The metadata standard used for cataloguing data refers to “the formal specification of the attributes (characteristics) employed for representing information resources” (Alemu and Stevens, 2015). According to Haslhofer and Klas (Haslhofer and Klas, 2010) a metadata schema is a set of elements with a precise semantic definition and optionally rules how and what values can be assigned to these elements; a metadata standard then is a schema which is developed and maintained by an institution that is a standard-setting one.

Unpicking the categories of metadata properties, their forms and their scope/level is another area of potential complexity and confusion.

2.2.1. Metadata properties

³¹ <https://fairsharing.org/collection/IVOA>

³² <https://www.nature.com/sdata/policies/repositories>

³³ <https://www.nature.com/articles/sdata201895>

Several metadata classification schemes propose that a metadata schema/standard associated with data cataloguing may support a range of functions, often with overlapping and conflicting terminology [Digital Curation Centre³⁴], Riley, 2017; Asmi *et al.*, 2019. We merge and summarise them in table 1.

Table 1 Metadata Properties

<i>Descriptive</i>	information about the entities such as identifier, type, location etc, often including the use of controlled vocabularies for classification and indexing and links to related resources . A precise idea about the content of a resource, so that users can find a resource and know if it is appropriate: a title, a description, keywords and one or many points of contact (creator, author, and editor) etc. Also called “functional” metadata.
<i>Technical</i>	technical processes used to produce, or required to use a digital object: type of resource, encoding format, file size, software used. Also called “operational”.
<i>Administrative</i>	administrative aspects such as IP rights and acquisition and information concerning the creation, alteration and version control of the metadata itself. Also called “operational”.
<i>Structural</i>	information about the files that make up the resource and the relationships between them.
<i>Use</i>	user access, user tracking and multi-versioning information.
<i>Preservation</i>	documents actions such as migrations and checksum calculations. Also called “operational”.

2.2.2. Metadata forms

The [FAIRsharing](#) catalogue categorises 4 forms that metadata may take (table 2). The Clusters often use different terminology.

Table 2 FAIRsharing terminology

³⁴ <https://www.dcc.ac.uk/guidance/briefing-papers/standards-watch-papers/what-are-metadata-standards>

<i>Terminology artifact</i>	The body of terms used with a particular technical application. Also called controlled vocabularies, ontologies and data dictionaries. e.g. EOSC-Life: The Plant Ontology, the Gene Ontology; an many 100s more; ENVRI-FAIR: The EnvO environment ontology;
<i>Model/format</i>	The data type for encoding the data in a prescribed form. e.g. EOSC-Life: mz peptide and protein Identification Markup Language, the SHHOC Structured Data Transformation Language (SDTL).
<i>Reporting guideline</i>	Describe a required set of data and metadata in the reporting of a particular class of experiment or type of data. Also known as a checklist, a minimum information model, common data elements or data schema. e.g. EOSC-Life: Minimum Information About a Plant Phenotyping Experiment; ESCAPE: IVOA Data Model for Astronomical DataSet Characterisation; the SHHOC Data Documentation Initiative for describing surveys, questionnaires, statistical data files, and social sciences study-level information
<i>Identifier schema</i>	The syntax and metadata associated with an identifier. e.g. the ESCAPE IVOA Identifier; EOSC-Life: accession numbers in repositories

2.2.3. Metadata scope/level and catalogue structures

Data catalogues manage multiple levels of content often reflecting their structure. Stratified metadata distinguish between:

- metadata about the catalogue itself
- metadata about datasets in the collection
- metadata about the data records within the dataset

In FAIRsFAIR (Riungu-Kalliosaari *et al.*, 2020) two levels are proposed: research information and research data.

- *research information* focusses on metadata and creating knowledge about the research at large (the administrative and use categories in table 1);
- *research data* focusses on expressing the structures of the data and managing the lifecycle and documentation to support things like reproducibility and transparency of the research for scientific benefit (the technical categories in table 1).

GO-FAIR's [FAIR Datapoint](#) proposes 5 layers of metadata for cataloging a dataset, forming a nested or hierarchical structure, primarily using the DCAT metadata standard.

Table 3: GO-FAIR metadata layers

<i>FAIR Data Point itself</i>	includes: name and version of the repository, dates, contact information, certification info, API etc.
<i>Catalogue level</i>	defines the catalogue, i.e., the collection of datasets. includes metadata about name of the catalogue, version, responsible organisation(s) or persons(s), description, dates
<i>Dataset level</i>	represents an individual dataset in the collection; name of the dataset, responsible organisation(s) or persons(s), version, description, dates and the dataset metadata schema it is supposed to conform to and provenance of the dataset
<i>Distribution level</i>	represents an accessible form of a dataset, e.g., a downloadable file or a web service that gives access to the data, including similar metadata to the dataset level
<i>Data record level</i>	the data record itself in the dataset, with similar metadata to dataset level, including the specification of the data record metadata schema

The **Catalogue - Dataset - Data Record** pattern appears widely, recognising that data resources are organised into datasets that can be composed of other datasets or specific data records (see Figure 1). This appears, for example, in the dataONE³⁵, Dryad³⁶, Zenodo.org, and GBIF³⁷ catalogues, and as separate Profiles in [Bioschemas](#), the schema.org based resource markup sponsored by the ELIXIR Life Science RI.

This layering introduces structure to unstructured records. For example, free text documents and arbitrary files will have structured metadata in the catalogue but be unstructured at the record level. For example, catalogues of clinical trial data or consent forms, the data are PDFs in the national native language; in generic repositories such as figshare or Zenodo the content are arbitrary files.

³⁵ <https://www.dataone.org/network/#list-of-member-repositories>

³⁶ <https://datadryad.org/>

³⁷ <https://www.gbif.org/>

Figure 1 - Datasets and records in data resources. On the right box a decomposed and simplified representation shows a data resource may be composed of 1 or more datasets and a dataset can be composed of more data records. Data resource maps to data catalogue for this deliverable. [EOSCpilot Deliverable [D6.3](#)].

This metadata stratification has a profound effect on which standards are used at each layer, the level of “FAIR compliance” that the catalogue can state a claim to, the depth of cross disciplinary catalogue integration and discoverability and the properties that are relevant to EOSC services:

- *similar and/or domain agnostic metadata properties* are used to describe data catalogues and datasets across different scientific domains, typically with shallow level of detail;
- *domain-specific metadata properties* related to the nature of the entity are described within data records, typically with deeper level of detail.

Examples of this pattern appear in the Clusters: for example the EOSC-Life ELIXIR European Genome-phenome Archive is a repository that has 5967 datasets within it.

The pattern is also important for catalogues that have Access Control mandates, for example those that handle sensitive data. Examples include the ECRIN MDR Metadata Repository for clinical trial data objects and the BBMRI-ERIC Samples Directory from the EOSC-Life Cluster. Access Control may be set at the Catalogue, Dataset or Data Record level, but typically the Dataset level.

SHHOC is typical of the Clusters, recommending domain-specific standards (for expressivity) typically at the Data Record level and common standards for (low-level) interoperability/discoverability typically at the Catalogue and Dataset level (Broeder *et al.* (2019).

2.3 Generic and specific metadata standards

A community's standard schema may be developed and maintained by nationally or internationally recognised centres of excellence, community or professional bodies, some of which may take on a statutory role for ratification and certification. Examples include: [Dublin Core Metadata Initiative](#), [DataCite](#), the [Open Geospatial Consortium](#), the [Global Alliance for Genomics and Health](#), the [International Virtual Observatory Alliance](#) and [Biodiversity Information Standards](#). A number of schemas or standards may be later ratified by professional, national or international bodies such as the [ICA](#) (International Council on Archives) and [ISO](#) (International Organization for Standardization). Appendix A1 highlights major organisations operating in data type specific standard specifications, which will be referred to in chapter 3 when we examine the RI Clusters.

2.3.1 Data type and domain specific standards

Typed metadata is defined with particular reference to a data type (for example, publication records, protein information, gene sequence, climate data), and will not be appropriate for use across different such types. It will refer to properties determined by the information embedded in the record itself, and is therefore data type specific. This metadata will therefore appear at the record level and may surface at the dataset and data catalogue level at perhaps more shallow levels of detail. Specific metadata standards come in all the forms described in table 2.

Appendix A1 lists examples of data type specific metadata standards used by the RIs, such as the Ecological Metadata Language, [ISO 19115](#) for describing geographic information and services and so on.

2.3.2 Generic metadata standards

Generic metadata is applicable across multiple data types, appearing at the data catalogue, dataset and data record levels and refers to properties of the catalogue, dataset or record rather than the content or type of information recorded. It can be broadly considered as *resource-specific*, rather than data type specific. Some of their properties also typically appear as the generic properties in the reporting guidelines or checklists of the specific standards (for example “keyword” or “name”).

A number of such generic vocabularies exist, largely created to address specific issues, or else to build or repurpose those that existed for a new purpose. Because so many exist it is common practice to develop cross-walks or mappings across the different schema.

Appendix A1 presents some of the more widely used metadata standards, and widely used de facto standards - that is - not ratified by a body but so widely used as to be considered a standard. These may be developed by commercial enterprises or widely used platforms.

Two standards merit special mention: DCAT and schema.org, given the historical relevance of DCAT, and the central role it has played in the development of the more modern and popularised web-based schema.org standard. We also highlight these two general metadata standards - DCAT and Schema.org - as they are prevalent across the Clusters, as well as detailing other standards, such as DataCite, which are prevalent in non Life Science centric repositories. The subset of the schema.org vocabulary for Dataset (properties and types) is inspired by DCAT version 1 (DCAT1), where direct equivalences can be mapped. Mapping of Dublin core to schemas.org have been made previously (2011³⁸). However, use cases for these vocabularies differ. DCAT seeks to model in detail datasets and catalogues, while schema.org is targeted to facilitating discoverability and indexing as performed by internet search engines. We include the crosswalk mapping in Appendix A1.

A set of definitions for common properties used across multiple data types and metadata schemas, is being proposed by the [RDA Data Metadata Interest Group](#), to facilitate cross-walk and common referencing.

³⁸ <https://dcmi.github.io/schema.org/mappings.html>

1. OpenAIRE-Guidelines for Data Archives

The [OpenAIRE Guidelines for Data Archive Managers](#) provides guidance for managers of Data archives and repositories (Institutional & thematic) and Catch-all Repositories to define and implement their local data management policies in exposing metadata for data products. They provide indications on how to make dataset products citable in order to make them first-level citizens of an Open Science interlinked scholarly communication ecosystem. The motivating principle is “not to reinvent the wheel”, and so relies on the widely-adopted [DataCite](#) schema as “application profile” structure, and identifies common standard vocabularies and formats, as defined by the community, to converge on semantic aspects.

By contributing to and implementing the OpenAIRE Guidelines, data archive managers will converge towards agreed on/common cross-discipline policies for data citation and description, establishing the stepping-stones for an “interlinked” data scholarly/publishing infrastructure for research. By adhering to the guidelines, visibility and re-use of repository content will be significantly increased. Today (Dec. 2020), 52 data archives are compatible with the Guidelines and the [Dataverse platform project](#) (starting from version v4.14) has embedded the Guidelines as an out-of-the box feature of Dataverse data repository instantiations.

The OpenAIRE Guidelines for Data Archive Managers are part of the larger package of [the OpenAIRE Guidelines](#), which supports the Guidelines as a community tool to define common metadata for citation policies across communities for publications, data, and software. Such a package will be part of the initial Resource Interoperability Framework for the [European Open Science Cloud \(EOSC\)](#). The extension of this package with OpenAIRE/EOSC community-specific guidelines is the use-case of Task 4.4, addressed by this deliverable and aims to include bioschemas.org as the first example of such patterns.

By adhering to the OpenAIRE Guidelines, data archives/repositories will include/onboard their research products into the [OpenAIRE Research Graph](#), making them visible/accessible as EOSC resources interlinked with publications, software, project, funders via several third-party consumers. Known consumers today include organizations (EC CORDIS, institutional sites and monitoring tools), researchers in the Science of Science-related topics, and companies (Elsevier’s Mendeley, Scopus, SciVal, Springer Nature, and many SMEs).

2. DCAT

DCAT is a recommendation of The World Wide Web Consortium (W3C), an [international community](#) that develops open [standards](#) to ensure the long-term growth of the Web.

[DCAT](#) is an RDF vocabulary designed to facilitate interoperability between data catalogs published on the Web, targeting datasets and data services. [DCAT2](#) is an improved version of DCAT to address deficiencies, especially with respect to identifiers and data citation issues. Although DCAT2 supersedes DCAT it maintains the DCAT namespace to retain backwards compatibility.

DCAT enables a publisher to describe datasets and data services in a catalog using a standard model and vocabulary that facilitates the consumption and aggregation of metadata from multiple catalogs. This can increase the discoverability of datasets and data services. It also makes it possible to have a *decentralized* approach to publishing data catalogues and *makes federated search for datasets across catalogues in*

multiple sites possible using the same query mechanism and structure. Aggregated DCAT metadata can serve as a manifest file as part of the digital preservation process.

DCAT terms are used at the Data Catalogue, Dataset and Data record levels (see Appendix A):

- [dcat:Catalog](#) represents a catalog, which is a dataset in which each individual item is a metadata record describing some resource; the scope of dcat:Catalog is collections of metadata about datasets or data services.
- [dcat:Resource](#) represents a dataset, a data service or any other resource that may be described by a metadata record in a catalog.
- [dcat:Dataset](#) represents a dataset. A dataset is a collection of data, published or curated by a single agent. Data comes in many forms including numbers, words, pixels, imagery, sound and other multi-media, and potentially other types, any of which might be collected into a dataset.
- [dcat:Distribution](#) represents an accessible form of a dataset such as a downloadable file.
- [dcat:DataService](#) represents a data service. A data service is a collection of operations accessible through an interface (API) that provides access to one or more datasets or data processing functions.
- [dcat:CatalogRecord](#) represents a metadata item in the catalog, primarily concerning the registration information, such as who added the item and when.

DCAT1 vocabulary borrows terms from Dublin Core [DC](#) and Friend of a Friend [FOAF](#). DCAT provides both a metadata model and API, and is recommended by major search engines such as Google. DCAT-AP was [recognised](#) in 2018 as a suitable way to represent and exchange research metadata between repositories, and between catalogues in domain-agnostic manner.

Most of the cluster's have catalogues within their RIs, or at the cluster level, that either use DCAT, map to DCAT, intend to map to DCAT or can map to DCAT.

3. Schema.org

[Schema.org](#) is a collection of structured data schemas that have been developed by a collaboration between internet search engines, including Google, Yahoo, Bing and Yandex. Schema.org markup is intended to be embedded in web pages and site maps, where it can be harvested by bots and indexed, aggregated and fed into Knowledge Graphs and registries. It is claimed that over 40% of web pages are marked up with schema.org - by the end of 2015, there were an estimated 12 million web pages using schema.org (Guha, R., Brickley, D. and Macbeth, S., 2015) - and it is a driver for search engines, including Google's Dataset search.

As the markup can be harvested from web pages it is a powerful mechanism for metadata acquisition without the need to implement APIs. The ethos of schema.org is to invert the registration and discovery orthodoxy. Rather than register a dataset (push), instead mark it up and let a search engine or indexer harvest it (pull) and make a registry. Schema.org is the basis of Google's [Dataset Search](#). Google have recently [released](#) a dataset with metadata for 3.5M datasets from their corpus -- these are datasets with DOIs and compact identifiers. In a recent [analysis](#) of Google Dataset Search, the geosciences are highlighted as [particularly successful](#) in making their data [FAIR](#).

Schema.org is built upon the concepts of types and their properties, for instance an 'organisation' ([type](#)) has properties including '[address](#)', '[employee](#)', and is a quick and convenient way to describe information on the web. Schema.org also describes data, particularly with respect to published (online) data available in repositories ([Dataset](#)), or collections of data ([DataCatalog](#)), and accompanying types and their properties (eg. [DataDownload](#)).

A few cluster projects have used, or have RIs that have used, Schema.org notably: EOSC-Life and ENVRI-FAIR. Efforts to use schema.org for research include:

- [Earth Science Information Partners \(ESIP\)](#) advice on schema.org use for GeoSciences
- [Schema: Extensions to schema.org to support structured, semantic, and executable documents](#)
- [Bioschemas: extensions to schema.org for Life Science resources](#)

4. Bioschemas

[Bioschemas](#) is an opinionated view of schema.org, tailored to better suit Life Science resources, developed by a community group sponsored by the ELIXIR Research Infrastructure but extending to partners in the EOSC-Life Cluster and the DISSCo Research Infrastructure.

Bioschemas (i) defines conventions for [Profiles](#) over the Schema.org types that identify and restricts the essential properties to use in describing a resource and (ii) proposes [new types and properties](#) to Schema.org to allow for the description of life science resources where this is found to be necessary. Although the prime use case for marking up resources is findability, there are additional use cases:

- A canonical encoding for machine processable metadata for tools such as workflows (e.g. release dates and versions) and between workflow systems (e.g. [encoding a profile for registering workflows](#) in the [EOSC-Life Workflow Hub](#) that is mapped to from community workflow management systems);
- The movement of metadata between resources without the need to implement APIs at the source (e.g. registering training materials in ELIXIR Training portal from content management systems and automating registry curation);

Reflecting the stratification of metadata for data cataloguing, Bioschemas has broadly two classes of markup level: Cataloging level and data type level (see figure 2).

Figure 2 - Bioschema's two classes of markup level: Cataloging level and data type level

[DataCatalog](#) and [Dataset](#) Profiles (the [DataRecord](#) profile is still in draft) are the most widely used, as one would expect, with 24 and 36 resources marked up, respectively. DataCatalogue proposes 5 mandatory, 8 recommended and 2 optional fields. When to use DataRecord rather than Dataset is still a hotly contested topic, with most resources adopting dataset. In November 2020 Bioschemas claim 100+ resources are marked up with Bioschemas. An obstacle to wider Bioschemas adoption has been the acceptance of new types by Schema.org. In a Catch-22 situation, dataset providers and registries are only willing to adopt the types if they are in schema.org, while schema.org will not accept the types unless they have already been used. As DataCatalog and Dataset are conventions for using “vanilla” schema.org this “new type” barrier is avoided and hence the profiles are more widely adopted, plus a resource or catalogue using these profiles is automatically compliant with Google’s Dataset search.

ResearchSchemas³⁹ is an RDA initiative to promote research data discoverability and accessibility exposing structured markup via schema.org (wider scope than the Bioschemas work which targets the Life Sciences). Since 2018 slow progress has been made on ResearchSchemas.

5. DataCite

DataCite⁴⁰ is an organisation that not only issues DOIs for research outputs such as publications, but also for datasets. Alongside this activity, it has been involved in sustained effort in providing a set of metadata that accompanies the DOIs that it issues. Those metadata comply with its published standard [metadata schema](#), which continues to be refined. The latest specification can be found here⁴¹. DataCite has been established in this arena for some time, and is a common standard applied in domain agnostic fashion.

6. [EDMI](#) (EOSC Datasets Minimum Information)

The EOSCpilot reports on Data Interoperability describe a federated ecosystem of resources, registries and catalogues and the metadata flow through this ecosystem. The focus of these deliverables was to demonstrate how to facilitate the availability of scientific data in EOSC, following three guiding principles which are worth repeating: reuse (leverage the rich legacy of RIs), least (minimal metadata for maximal benefit) and practical (sustainable and pragmatic delivery) (Asmi *et al.*, 2017).

To build an interconnected federation of data catalogues, drawing upon contributions and surveys of several Research Infrastructures (including ENVRI, EPOS and ELIXIR), EOSCpilot proposed (Asmi *et al.*, 2017b) the [EDMI](#) (EOSC Datasets Minimum Information). This is a minimum information metadata guideline to help users and services to find and access datasets reusing existing data models and interfaces. It relies on existing standards to promote operational metadata required by services. It recommends [metadata properties](#) that would be a common dataset used across research domains. EDM I properties are defined in two categories: functional (exposing scientific metadata) and operational (exposing technical metadata).

EDMI was not intended to be a standard itself, but rather to specify a **minimal checklist** of essential or core information, producing a crosswalk [mapping](#) between the properties and other commonly used metadata models such as schema.org, DataCite (v4.1) and DATS (Data Article Tag Suite; Sansone *et al.*, 2017). These mappings bridge between terms already in use across catalogues and map to aggregator catalogues developed by the Research Infrastructures clusters.

³⁹ RDA Data Discovery Paradigms Interest Group <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/data-discovery-paradigms-ig>

⁴⁰ <https://datacite.org/>

⁴¹ https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.3/doc/DataCite-MetadataKernel_v4.3.pdf

Figure 3. Representation of a minimum set of metadata properties used in different data models. On the left, circles represent metadata properties (minimum properties) to be exposed to help EOSC services and users to find metadata. The coloured boxes represent different data models containing different properties, including the minimum set of metadata properties, which can be mapped across data models (solid line). Note: equivalent properties across metadata models are often named differently.

Since 2018 there has been no further work on EDM1 and no adoption. The crosswalks to schema.org, DCAT and other metadata schemas are out of date. However, many of the properties are found in [Bioschemas.org profiles](https://bioschemas.org/profiles) for DataCatalogue and Dataset. Appendix A1 gives the EDM1 properties as they stood in 2018.

7. DDI-CDI: Cross Domain Integration

The Data Documentation Initiative (DDI) Alliance recently [announced](#) the first Public Review of DDI – Cross Domain Integration (DDI-CDI), a [specification](#) aimed at helping implementers integrate data across domain and institutional boundaries. The DDI Alliance has produced specifications aimed at the Social, Behavioral, and Economic (SBE) sciences. DDI-CDI is designed to serve a broader audience, reflecting the need across many different domains to exchange and reuse data which comes from outside the traditional range of data sources. It is meant to be used as a stand-alone specification for data integration in any domain or combination of domains and it can be used in combination with existing DDI specifications (e.g., DDI-Codebook and DDI-Lifecycle).

To quote the announcement “DDI-CDI focuses on a uniform approach to describing a range of needed data formats (traditional wide/rectangular data, long [event] data, multi-dimensional data, and NoSQL/key-value data) which allows them to be connected and understood to support transformation and processing for integrated use. It is explicitly designed to work with many popular generic technology standards such as PROV-O, BPMN, DCAT, SDMX, DataCube, SSN/SOSA and [Schema.org](https://schema.org) to allow for easy integration into systems which support them. DDI-CDI is aligned with other DDI specifications (DDI-Codebook, DDI-Lifecycle) to support integration of external data in systems which use DDI.”

The idea of DDI-CDI is a universal common model to describe data and its provenance at a detailed, machine-actionable level in order to bridge and integrate datasets described in different formats (e.g. DCAT or schema.org) along with processes and provenance. At 67 pages of dense spec it is certainly a substantial effort at a single model that attempts to tie all other models together.

The implication is that catalogues would be required to change their models to comply with it or they would need to map to it. Whichever case, the cost is high against unclear benefits when compared to lighter weight approaches like DCAT and schema.org, and simple cross-walks (DCAT is already mapped to Schema.org) to meet a demand. The SSHOC cluster will likely pursue this approach (given its origins), whereas EOSC-Life will likely adopt a lightweight cross-mapping approach (see section 3). FAIRsFAIR and CODATA are strong advocates of DDI-CDI.

2.4 FAIR Catalogues

The FAIRsFAIR project reports ([D2.1 Report on FAIR requirements for persistence and interoperability 2019](#), [D2.2 FAIR Semantics: First recommendations](#), [D2.3 Set of FAIR data repositories features](#) and [D2.4 2nd Report on FAIR requirements for persistence and interoperability](#)) give a thorough study of the FAIR principles applied to data catalogues and repositories.

From a FAIR perspective (Wilkinson *et al.*, 2016; Mons *et al.*, 2020)⁴², a metadata standard serves to support different levels of Find, Access, Interoperate and Reuse, with the metadata encoded in a machine-processable format as well as human-readable:

- *Findable*: the metadata necessary to catalogue a dataset into a searchable registry or to mark up a dataset so that it might be indexed by a search engine
- *Accessible*: the metadata necessary to report support access protocols and content negotiation
- *Interoperable*: the metadata necessary to standardise common content so that the data catalogued might be combined with other data - from a cataloguing perspective this could be reporting the domain specific data reporting standards and formats that the data claims to be compliant with or expects of any data to be catalogued
- *Reusable*: the metadata necessary to report licenses, provenance and domain specific data reporting standards and formats.

Note that FAIRsFAIR among others makes a distinction between services that are FAIR themselves and services that make data more FAIR. The ELIXIR covid19portal is an example of "a service that makes data more FAIR" without being FAIR itself.

The notion of Shallow and Deep FAIR for the contents of catalogues refers to the extent of the metadata returned on a PID resolution of an entry in the catalogue (Table 4). In the same way that catalogue metadata is stratified, so FAIR indicators (metrics) must also be stratified.

FAIRsharing registers metrics that the community have developed to, ultimately, automate the test for FAIRness of a repository or catalogue, and its [FAIRAssist](#) extension is a first step to list and describe existing resources for the assessment and/or evaluation of digital objects against the FAIR principles. The current focus is on manual questionnaires, checklists and automated tests that help users understand how to achieve a state of "FAIRness", and how this can be measured and improved.

Table 4 - Inspired by Thierry Sengstag and Sofia Georgakopoulou⁴³ CC-BY-4.0 and presented in D2.4

	Research Information	Research Data
Shallow FAIR	Outputs: DOI; URN; ARK People: ORCID	Core descriptive metadata that includes necessary research information PIDs (or at least some reference metadata like controlled vocabularies), machine readable licences.
Deep FAIR	All elements expressed with persistent identifiers All relation expressed as graphs	All data elements are machine accessible and the integrity is ensured

⁴² RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model WG, <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/fair-data-maturity-model-wg>

⁴³ https://www.swissuniversities.ch/fileadmin/swissuniversities/Dokumente/Organisation/SUK-P/SUK_P-2/2019_OpenScience_Poster12_RDM_UniBas_20190909_fundingFAIRcommunities.pdf

	(Citations expressed as graphs)	
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Shallow and deep FAIR recognises that FAIRness applies across the same spectrum as the metadata.

- FAIRness of the catalogue itself
- FAIRness of the datasets in the collection
- FAIRness of data within the dataset

FAIRsFAIR presents guidelines to enable features for repositories (and data catalogues) which allow them to host FAIR digital objects **and be FAIR themselves** (Behnke *et al.*, 2020). The recommendations are summarised in Tables 5 and 6.

Table 5 - Proposed organisational and operational features for FAIR Catalogues from FAIRsFAIR [D2.3 Set of FAIR data repositories features](#)

Organisational	Other
<p>The repository itself should have a PID (FA)</p> <p>The repository needs to be listed in registries of repositories (F)</p> <p>Explicit data deletion policy - explicit roles and responsibilities (I)</p> <p>Different access policies for different versions of the data (A)</p> <p>Technical support for predefined file formats (I)</p> <p>Reuse of community standards and ontologies from public registries (FI)</p> <p>Use of PIDs as the manifestation of a data policy (I)</p> <p>Only mint one PID per digital object, collection or what one wants to identify (IR)</p> <p>Explicit data policies (like versioning and dynamic data) and PID policies in human and machine interoperable way (FAIR)</p> <p>Documentation of interfaces and APIs (FAIR)</p>	<p><i>The repository should:</i></p> <p>Support dynamic data sets (f.e. time series data)</p> <p>Send notifications to the creator if similar data appears elsewhere</p> <p>Publication tracker for associated datasets</p> <p>Have clear Service Level Agreements</p> <p>Allow citation or reuse of partial data or single elements of datasets</p> <p>Have downloadable citations (BibTeX) that point to the data</p> <p>Variety of access restrictions</p> <p>Tombstone procedure</p> <p><i>The repository search interface should have high usability.</i></p> <p><i>Repository staff should:</i></p> <p>Provide training on APIs</p> <p>“Spend time being a researcher to better understand the challenges they have making data available in a way that supports findability.”</p>

Table 6 - Proposed technical features for FAIR Catalogues from FAIRsFAIR

Technical			
Metadata for digital objects	PID policies	Data object and file	Repository

<p>The repository should provide metadata in different formats, which can be harvested by different search engines (I)</p> <p>Metadata should be provided as RDF, including JSON-LD. Based on these machines can provide human-friendly presentations/visualisations by resolving the URIs and retrieving the human-readable labels (I)</p> <p>Providing metadata at the level of files, variables, attributes, individual cells, granularity to be decided by the repository (I)</p> <p>Gather provenance metadata on digital objects and files upon upload (IR)</p> <p>Provide masks and ways to quickly upload metadata (I)</p> <p>Demand fine-grained metadata from data providers (FI)</p> <p>Implement community standards (FI)</p> <p>Automatic ontology suggestions and lookup (IF)</p> <p>Landing pages should be machine-interpretable or implement content negotiation, have metadata in different formats (FI)</p> <p>HTTP header should contain technical metadata about the DO (FI)</p>	<p>PID for each digital object or file (I)</p> <p>Use global persistent identifiers (I)</p> <p>The target of PID should be inferable by machines from PID metadata itself, employ PID information types or Linked Data type (I)</p>	<p>Connect compute infrastructures and data repositories (to avoid commuting data) (I)</p> <p>Subsetting of data (I)</p> <p>Technical support for predefined file formats (including complex data formats like netCDF), with a preference for open file formats (FI)</p>	<p>The repository itself should have a PID (FA)</p> <p>Machine-readable and interpretable metadata about repository itself (I)</p> <p>Expose (Meta) Data Model (in machine-readable form) (I)</p> <p>Machine-readable license (R)</p> <p>The repository should provide a search interface or be linked to aggregating services that enable findability (F)</p>
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Google Dataset Search recently published a [best practice guide](#) for FAIR datasets:

1. *Discoverability* Dataset metadata should be on pages that are accessible to web crawlers and that provide metadata in machine-readable formats in order to improve discoverability.
2. *Persistence* Publishing metadata on sites that are likely to be more persistent than personal web pages will facilitate data reuse and citation. Many URLs that hosted a dataset one day did not have it a few weeks or months later. Data repositories, such as [Figshare](#), [Zenodo](#), [DataDryad](#), [Kaggle Datasets](#) are singled out for praise.
3. *Provenance* With datasets often published in multiple repositories, it would be useful for repositories to describe the provenance information more explicitly in the metadata. The provenance information helps users understand who collected the data, where the primary source of the dataset is, or how it might have changed across repositories (eg. value-add).

4. *Licensing* Datasets should include licensing information, ideally in a machine-readable format. Our analysis indicates that when dataset providers select a license, they tend to choose a fairly open one. So, encouraging and enabling scientists to choose licenses for their data will result in many more datasets being openly available.
5. *Assigning persistent identifiers (such as DOIs)* DOIs are critical for long-term tracking and useability. Not only do these identifiers allow for much easier citation of datasets and version tracking, they are also dereferenceable: if a dataset moves, the identifier can point to a different location.

Requirements documents have been developed by the Cluster projects:

- **EOSC-Life** has preliminarily [proposed](#) FAIR requirements for EOSC-Life datasets, which also may apply to EOSC-Life registries and catalogues for data and other research objects, and the FAIR requirements on provenance, which includes the requirements of a common provenance model, and the provenance of physical and digital objects.
- **ENVRI-FAIR** by its name proposes to embrace the FAIR principles⁴⁴, including provenance⁴⁵ to build the ENVRI KnowledgeBase⁴⁶.
- **ESCAPE** has finalised a concept note - [ESCAPE Open-source Scientific Software and Service Repository \(OSSR\)](#) - to develop a repository as a trusted entry point where researchers can safely archive their data, software, documentation and tutorials, for long-term preservation and retrieval adhering to the FAIR Principles.
- **PaNOSC** has published its FAIR Data Policy Framework⁴⁷

2.5 Cataloging Research Objects other than data

Many of the Clusters have the need to catalogue objects other than data. For example:

- *Software and tools*: in EOSC-Life: [bio.tools](#), the ELIXIR registry of tools, uses the EDAM ontology and Bioschemas markup to describe its metadata; [Biocontainers](#) is a registry of containers; in PaNOSC: the [PaNdata software catalogue](#) is a database of software used mainly for data analysis of neutron and photon experiments. ESCAPE plans the ESCAPE OSSR and SHHOC is developing a Service Catalogue that includes software⁴⁸.
- *Computational workflows*: Computational workflows are a specific type of software/tool. EOSC-Life has built a Cluster level catalogue for workflows [WorkflowHub](#), which operates in an ecosystem of workflow management systems and repositories - the workflows remain and evolve in their native repositories in native form. The makers are custodians of their own workflows, so transparent attribution & credit are critical. Similar to data, the Workflow Hub has defined a minimum information model or data schema for common registration metadata (defined in [Bioschemas](#)), and uses the [Common Workflow Language](#) as a canonical workflow description.

⁴⁴ <https://envri.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/Towards-Operational-RIs-with-FAIR-Data-and-Services.pdf>

⁴⁵ <https://envri.eu/envri-book/>

⁴⁶ <https://envri-fair.github.io/knowledge-base-ui/>

⁴⁷ <https://www.panosc.eu/data/panosc-data-policy-framework/>

⁴⁸ <https://envri.eu/envri-book/>

- *Models*: Computational workflows are a specific type of software/tool. From EOSC-Life [Biomodels](#) and [JWS Online](#) are examples of repositories for computational models. Such models have their own standards (SBML, SBOL, SED-ML) that record parameters, versions and support reproducibility, as well as Minimum Information guidelines ([MIRIAM](#)) which specify metadata requirements to achieve compliance to that community standard. Models are equally important in the other Clusters.

These are registries in that they aim to be complete, though do not contain the actual software or workflows but rather pointers to them, and give each entry an identifier. They also tend to have limited domain specificity as their focus is not on the scientific domain *per se*, but on the type or analytic methodology (tool, software, workflow). Although model registries are more tailored, reporting guidelines, terminology and identifiers tend to be generic. Domain-specific markup is confined to ontology terms used to label the objects, lending semantics to the data. They also distinguish themselves from cataloguing data in several other ways, some of which are listed below:

- Software is inherently an evolving and living entity that needs to be updated, so versioning and release information is essential;
- Software is inherently compound, made up of multiple and interdependent components authored by many developers over time;
- Software is frequently forked and cloned, making tracing and tracking variants a feature of their cataloguing;
- Smooth integration and auto registration with, say, workflow execution platforms is highly desirable through APIs such as Tool Registry Service (TRS) API for exchanging tools and workflows.

FAIR principles for workflows need to address their specific nature in terms of their composition of executable software steps, their provenance, and their development (Goble *et al.*, 2020), as does all software (Lamprecht *et al.*, 2020). The [RDA FAIR 4 Research Software](#) WG is setting out to develop FAIR principles that include software and workflow catalogues.

Other research object types include:

- Standard Operating Procedures and Lab Protocols (e.g. [Protocols.io](#))
- Training materials (e.g. EOSC-Life RI ELIXIR, [TeSS ELIXIR training portal](#), [ENVRI-FAIR Training catalogue](#))
- Physical materials such as samples, specimens, people (e.g. [ECRIN Centralised MDR Metadata Repository](#) for clinical trial data objects;)

These are typically PDF or other forms of documents, where the metadata is at the “dataset or data record” level, that is, metadata is about the object but there is no machine-processable metadata structuring the object itself. Bioschema.org profiles are being developed for registering some of these objects.

Some Research Infrastructures have cataloguing solutions that *interlink* data, models, workflows and protocols in investigations. The SHHOC marketplace has modest ambitions in this direction. The ESFRIs ISBE⁴⁹(Systems Biology) and IBISBA (Industrial Biotechnology) combine all these object forms in their investigations. Both use the [FAIRDOME-SEEK](#) to build Hubs ([FAIRDOMEHub](#), [IBISBAHub](#)) that form an integrated catalogue referencing objects that remain stored in their native repositories or public catalogues/archives. These objects are of different types. This federated approach organises and relates the objects and their roles in an investigation using the [ISA](#) (Investigation, Study, Assay) metadata schema (see figure 4). The approach means that context of an investigation is retained whilst the objects can be deposited in the authoritative

⁴⁹ <https://project.isbe.eu/>

repositories of the community or secure behind authentication and authorisation frameworks if they are sensitive.

Figure 4: FAIRDOMHub, investigation cataloguing model, data and SOP that may be held in different and securely accessed repositories.

3. Disciplinary metadata cataloguing across EOSC Enhance partner RIs and clusters

The Clusters typically operate within a federation of resources, registries and catalogues with their respective disciplinary metadata flowing through this ecosystem (Asmi *et al.*, 2017). EOSCpilot proposed principles for such a federation, focusing on **minimum metadata standards, mapping between different metadata models and reuse, light and practicality.**

- **Reuse:** Rely on metadata from RI metadata catalogues and support an ecosystem of catalogues and metadata flow, and provide quality recommendations to feedback to RIs, leaving FAIR data to be the responsibility of the RIs.
- **Light:** Focus on common and minimum metadata across metadata catalogues, common data types across different scientific disciplines, and technical service requirements and operational metadata while supporting flexible metadata models to embrace domain specifics.
- **Practical:** Engage with existing data repositories and catalogues in RIs, reusing methods to expose dataset metadata through metadata catalogues that are simple to implement and easy to sustain with guidelines and demonstrators.

The importance of an integrated ecosystem is highlighted by the EOSCpilot project, which was funded as part of the first phase in the development of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). It was tasked with developing pilots that integrate services and infrastructures, demonstrating interoperability and subsequent benefits across scientific domains.

EOSCpilot made the following recommendations towards the EOSC:

- The data guidelines and technical solutions proposed by EOSC should be specific, common, simple, lightweight and collaborative;
- All the data resources comprising the EOSC should expose structured metadata;
- The EOSC should reuse existing standard formats promoting the use of common best practices across scientific domains;
- The EOSC should propose minimum information guidelines across scientific domains especially encouraging exposing key operational metadata important for services consuming data;
- The EOSC should support an interconnected system of metadata catalogues as a fundamental service component to facilitate data discovery;
- The EOSC should implement a monitoring service to validate standards and recommendations proposed by the EOSC.

A cataloguing ecosystem encompasses a variety of metadata ingest pipelines; metadata feeds from individual resources to individual catalogues; domain, community and type-focused catalogues must feed more generic catalogues; generic catalogues and ‘catalogues of catalogues’ feed at appropriate granularity to the EOSC. Simultaneously, each feed mechanism, however implemented, collects a trace back path and provenance mechanism allowing reverse path interrogation of data at the original source. Such trace back mechanisms are seen in resources such as the ELIXIR TeSS training catalogue, the EOSC-Life WorkflowHub as well as other Cluster catalogues.

We describe properties, components, reference architecture, strategies, and standards used in catalogue integration. Useful general studies include Data Catalog Reference Model and Market Study⁵⁰ and 10 tip to building a successful data catalogue⁵¹.

3.1 Approaches to Cataloguing

As discussed in section 2, catalogues vary in the scope, depth and granularity of the metadata for their product entries. They also vary in their approaches.

3.1.1 Primary vs Secondary (Derived) Data

Primary data is raw data can be a large data set (e.g observation data) or a longitudinal data (e.g. social science survey data), while *secondary data* can be the result of processing or aggregation, resulting in derived knowledge, and a data set that occupies less computational storage. Both require provenance metadata; each may be subject to different access rights and embargos. For example, raw patient data (in EOSC-Life) will be closed with thin metadata, but derived aggregated data that is anonymised may be widely available. Acquisition and curation subsystems for raw data are a particular concern for many Clusters, especially for those where the observations cannot be repeated (e.g. astronomical (ESCAPE) or seismic (ENVRI) readings).

3.1.2 Catalogue scope

⁵⁰ <https://www.cc-cdq.ch/data-catalogs>

⁵¹ <https://community.alteryx.com/t5/Analytics/10-Tips-to-Build-a-Successful-Data-Catalog/ba-p/109870>

Where a catalogue is being established, there are a number of considerations that must be taken into account, besides those of direct scope. These will play a direct and major role in what will, and will not, be suitable metadata to be exposed through web interfaces, search functionality, and likely in download or export formats. These factors include:

Content scope

If the content of the catalogue is broad or has to cover many disciplines the metadata associated with each entry tends towards high level and discipline-agnostic (e.g. [OpenAIRE Research Graph](#), [B2FIND](#)). Homogeneous datasets and catalogues specify that the individual data sets or objects are all of the same type (format, metadata model, content/data type), while heterogeneous data sets that may be all entirely different from each other, or differ in a known number of ways (format, metadata model, content or data type). Hence SSHOC's recommendation that we can only use common standards for (low-level) interoperability/discoverability and must use domain-specific standards (for expressivity).

Complexity of data and relationships between data sets

Where the hosting catalogue is a 'generic' host, capturing multiple data types and accommodating multiple formats or records, the relationship between datasets and other objects (scripts, derived datasets) is added value. The SSHOC marketplace, ENVRI flagship catalogue, and the PaNOSC data catalogue all aim to do this to varying degrees; the IBISBAHub of IBISBA already does. Such catalogues have to support multiple metadata models for detail and generic metadata for discovery to have broad coverage and applicability. For more complex data, where there are relations between different data sets and multiple layers of granularity embedded within, such issues as appropriate metadata models per data set are even more complicated.

Variations of scale – structures atomic resolution to population-level data

Broad scope cataloguing will usually approach variation of scale using a generic, high-level metadata model; it would be difficult to utilise a metadata model that alone could handle such variations of scale ranging for subatomic to astronomy data.

The number of datasets – from boutique but special to large enterprises

Another consideration for catalogues will be the total amount of data that it may be required to host; specialist catalogues focused on a niche data type, with limited researchers in the field would require much less data hosting real estate than say a research-active area of imaging.

3.1.3 Governance of catalogue: policy and authority for governance and catalogue recommendation

RIs vary in their governance authority and cataloguing autonomy ranging across the spectrum from complete delegation to the resource provider to complete control by the RI. To what extent are the catalogues "owned" by the RI, their national node nodes and partners.

RIs vary in the extent to which they assert where data and other research objects should be catalogued and how: from mandatory compliance through to strong recommendations, to informational guidelines and community norms (through, say, journal recommendations). This significantly impacts the extent of the comprehensiveness of the coverage of the catalogues.

Examples: ELIXIR indirectly recommends registries and resources where data may be deposited or catalogued through its recommended 'Deposition Databases', 'Recommended Interoperability Resources' and 'Tools' registries. But these are not compulsory or policed, and it is convenience, convention and community norms that drive cataloguing. The Resources are independently governed by their resource providers or national nodes but adhere to a common governance criteria. The same for the RIs as there is no data resource governance for datasets across EOSC-Life. The PaNOSC Data Policy Framework has been created as a guide and to be implemented at partner facilities. SHHOC Open Marketplace has a stronger drive to collect metadata against the CDI-DDI.

3.1.4 Access control: open vs highly managed control

Many RI catalogues are open and freely accessible. However, some RIs are working with highly sensitive and confidential datasets that require access control and transparent adherence to data usage against consent and careful provenance tracking of use. The obvious cases are health data in the EOSC-Life cluster but there are others including societal sensitive social science (SSHOC), biodiversity (DISSCo) and food security data and economically sensitive embargoed data in industrial biotechnology (IBISBA). In a few cases the catalogues allow progressive liberalisation in the access permissions, from private/enclave access to open (for example the IBISBA RI's IBISBAHub).

Controlled access to sensitive/private data leads to thin metadata that is shared, specific data models, specialised APIs and standards for usage access.

Example: EOSC-Life uses GA4GH standards such as: Data Use Ontology⁵² (usage restrictions expressed as machine readable markup), Beacon API⁵³ for genomic variants (indicating a yes/no answer to a limited set of questions) and GA4GH Passports for access policies⁵⁴. PaNOSC has support for embargoed data, which can only be accessed at the facility by authentication and authorisation access controls.

3.1.5 Degree of curation of content and collections

The degree to which content and associated metadata are actively curated. Curation can be delegated to the contributors or through catalogue dedicated effort. Some resources have a gatekeeping process but not an active curation process; some have automated curation processes. Expectations of the degree of compliance and validation against metadata fields also vary from strong compliance (so that metadata is expected) to light compliance (much of the metadata is optional and may be absent). Equally the degree of provenance collected - where did this data come from - varies from detailed tracking to lightweight.

Examples: [bio.tools](#) in EOSC-Life's ELIXIR is curated as a best effort by its contributors and has lee-way in its compliance to its metadata. Collections of tools are maintained and provenance is light touch, whereas the ELIXIR Core Data Resources and Data Depositions Resources are highly curated by dedicated teams. The SSHOC marketplace will be highly curated, improving the curation of its contributing catalogues.

⁵² <https://github.com/EBISPOT/DUO>

⁵³ <https://github.com/ga4gh-beacon/specification>

⁵⁴ https://github.com/ga4gh-duri/ga4gh-duri.github.io/blob/master/researcher_ids/ga4gh_passport_v1.md#passport

3.1.6 Architecture: Centralised, federated, decentralised

RIs vary in the architecture of their data cataloguing, ranging across the spectrum from completely centralised single catalogue to a managed federation of catalogues to fully decentralised collection of resources catalogued through additional services. Of course, an RI Cluster may have all of these, including catalogues of catalogues.

Examples: EOSC-Life has such a range of different and heterogenous RIs in its cluster, such that a single centralised metadata catalogue is deemed infeasible and not particularly useful other than at the highest level of registering the data resources across EOSC-Life directly in a [FAIRsharing collection](#), through tagging. ECRIN's MDR is a centralised, managed catalogue. BBMRI's MDR is centralised operating in a managed federation of biobanking registries that feed it. ELIXIR's Omics datasets are a decentralised collection federated by common use of shared metadata markup (omics and bioschema); the OmicsDI aggregator, aggregating across experimental and sample metadata from 23 open life sciences molecular databases.

The SSHOC cluster proposes a centralised marketplace of high-quality metadata contributed by source catalogues using a decoupled software architecture where the API is the main connection point for ingestion/enrichment/and relationship making. Sources (e.g. metadata catalogues) are ingested with the help of dedicated tools and manual mapping of sources to a data model / vocabularies and a history of changes: versioning and merging of items (identify the same item at different sources).

The PaNOSC cluster proposes two routes for opening datasets: Harvesting and custom search. Only simple metadata is harvested for a common catalogue. The rich metadata stays at the facility and is accessed by a custom search.

ENVRI-FAIR prototypes its ingestion pipeline based in the e-VRE metadata acquisition and retrieval workflow⁵⁵. The ENVRI-Reference Model separates the data acquisition and curation subsystems⁵⁶

⁵⁵ <https://envri.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/Data-Cataloguing.pdf>

⁵⁶ <https://envri.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/The-ENVRI-Reference-Model.pdf>

Figure 5: e-VRE metadata acquisition and retrieval workflow: metadata records are acquired from multiple sources, mapped to CERIF RDF and stored in the VRE catalogue; authenticated VRE users then query data via the e-VRE.

3.1.7 Ingest and harmonisation pipelines

The strategy adopted by various cataloguing efforts may also depend on whether content and associated catalogue-relevant metadata is acquired through automated harvesting and pipelines or by manual deposition and update. Some catalogues act through an aggregation mechanism, acquiring content through push feeds, pull harvesting or manual deposition; acquired catalogue products may originate from other catalogues, or a catalogue of catalogues (where the product itself is a catalogue). It is also important to point out the scope, scale and methodologies employed to express appropriate metadata for cataloguing:

Although the individual RIs may have different architectural approaches they all have some form of data/metadata harmonisation and processing pipelines. Harmonisation may be upstream a source or downstream at target. Both need accepted standards, compliance and validation and vary on whether the onus lies on the researchers/facilities that create the data or a broker into the catalogue. The content and associated metadata may be ingested through automated harvesting, automated feeds or by manual deposition, and may be validated by manual or automated means. Aggregated content and associated metadata may be harvested from other catalogues or the product is another catalogue often providing additional value.

As described in section 2, RIs have a plethora of metadata models, many of generic use, some with additional modifications to be more suited for particular use cases, and others which combine multiple vocabularies/properties into a new model. Ultimately, many of these properties cover the same ground, but often using a different 'property name', a conceptually identical but lexically different 'description', or even with different expectations on what would be considered valid 'values' for the property in question. Hence, there have been various efforts to 'map' different terms from different vocabularies and metadata models to navigate this equivalence, though these may still vary with respect to accepted 'values' for those properties. Mapping entails format conversions, content packaging and semantic mapping based on standardised vocabularies.

Catalogue acquisition and aggregation often requires functions and services for mapping if the source resources are not already harmonised with the catalogue. This is common in generic and highly aggregated catalogues such as the ENVRI-FAIR flagship catalogue.

A minimal metadata model, required for discoverability in a domain agnostic way, should define the key properties to optimise such discoverability, preferably with a description of how different vocabularies and metadata models map to those core properties that have been identified: [EDMI](#) is and CDI-DDI are examples; other approaches are crosswalks where necessary. The main issue is, what is minimal, as discussed in section 2.

3.1.8 Exemplar strategies for submission pipelines

Unified submission is a simple means to deal with varying metadata selections at source/origin documenting which properties are required by the (final) hosting solution - this places the onus strictly with the data owner/generator to provide the data with the additional necessary metadata to comply and qualify for inclusion in the catalogue. Of course, this may require the data generator to perform some ‘wrangling’ tasks, such as mapping their existing terminologies to those fields accepted by the destination hosting resource, where the development of either metadata model has not been informed by the other (developed independently).

Example: The EBI data submission portal⁵⁷ provides a bulk upload service for the ELIXIR Data Deposition Databases that are maintained by EMBL-EBI, using a common submission interface API. Documentation is provided to detail the metadata requirements for such bulk uploads⁵⁸ for each data type that is being uploaded, with a validation step during submission. Documentation is provided to guide users based on the ultimate hosting solution, by data type. For example, ‘sample’ schema can be found on github⁵⁹; while checklists for the different kinds of ‘sample’ hosted can be found [here](#). In this way, the EBI data submission portal ensures compliance to specific database (final host) resources through both syntactic and semantic validation.

Common model mapping shifts the burden from the data generator, and accommodates it within the submission pipeline of the hosting solution (e.g. a portal or catalogue). In this pattern, the mapping between the metadata model used by the data generator would be mapped to the (internal) metadata model employed by the hosting solution.

Structurally agnostic submission recognises the difference between *structured vs unstructured* data in the generating source and host catalogue. Catalogue registered content may be unstructured files or structured and expected to adhere to a metadata standard and format that might be validated on registration. The registration entry in the catalogue is structured against the catalogue’s schema, while the source of that content (the ‘harvested’ content) may itself be either structured (known properties, expected values, expressed formally, according to some *other* metadata model) or unstructured (values expressed following expected ‘range’ but not marked up according to a defined metadata schema). In this way, while metadata is provided by the source, it is not necessarily exposed by the host catalogue *per se*, since it is at the wrong

⁵⁷ <https://submission.ebi.ac.uk/api/docs/about.html>

⁵⁸ https://submission.ebi.ac.uk/api/docs/guide_file_upload.html

⁵⁹ <https://github.com/EBIBioSamples/biosamples-v4/blob/dev/webapps/core/src/main/resources/schemas/core/sample.json>

level of granularity, or the complexity is not representable, or desired to be represented, or is outside of the scope of the catalogue.

3.2 Access properties of catalogues

Those Clusters that are developing cluster level catalogues (SHHOC, ESCAPE, ENVRI-FAIR, PaNOSC) aim to offer the following facilities/functionality. EOSC-Life makes recommendations for its member RI Catalogues:

- *Discoverability support* - discoverability of the catalogue, of its hosted products/metadata, provenance mechanism to trace back sources, with appropriate web search and/or machine accessible and well documented API
- *Access to the products support* - each of the products provided with guidance as to their use and/or limitations, with links back to the origin of the product, its path into the catalogue, and direct support for the product (at source if not provided at the level of the catalogue)
- *Other catalogues or other systems harvest or access the catalogue content* - exchange and synchronisation mechanisms are available and documented to enable numerous and diverse catalogues to exist in an ecosystem of such resources, enabling pseudo-‘federated’ search, through a limited number of access points, leveraging the interconnectedness of the ecosystem.
- *Export/access formats supported* - input and output from a specific catalogue defined in accordance with established *and* generic standards; domain specific formats should also be accommodated where possible. Access mechanisms follow predictable and standard methodologies.
- *FAIR indicators supported* - while FAIR indicators themselves are still evolving, some indication of how ‘FAIR’ an individual dataset itself is automated at the level of the catalogue (automated evaluation on registration), or else resurfaced after harvesting from the original source (automated or manual evaluation on generation). The means of this evaluation must be documented, and should be provided with sufficient information for a re-evaluation to be undertaken.
- *KGs and added value* - a highly interconnected ecosystem of metadata catalogues could function as, or participate towards, a Knowledge Graph allowing the different resources (potentially holding different information) to be crossed queried and accumulate a potentially rich set of ‘value-added’ information from those resources.

3.3. Catalogue users

Important considerations in the creation and utility of a data catalogue are the users or actors who will interact with it. We summarise the classification of those actors from a recent series of articles (Zhao and Hellström, 2020), focusing on ENVRIplus architecture, from the perspective of interoperability of catalogues cross-RIs. Other comparable or extended lists of such users are available elsewhere⁶⁰.

- External users - researchers outside the specific RI, focused on data-driven science.
- Internal users - individuals inside an RI, including researchers, operators, project coordinators & data managers.
- RI Stakeholders - decision-makers and funders of the RI who need to have a broad picture of the Research Infrastructure resources in the European landscape to control their efficiency and complementarity.

⁶⁰ <https://www.cc-cdq.ch/data-catalogs>

- Policymakers - those using ENVRI information to develop governmental policies and laws.

3.4 Access, export and exchange formats and protocols

De facto and ratified standards for formats are used by data repositories, and for import/export around an ecosystem of data catalogues, repositories, applications and platforms. Again the landscape is one of generic, widely used standards and specific formats/protocols developed by communities. Programmatic access to catalogues - to search, deposit, access content, harvest, index and exchange product metadata, is essential to support a federated catalogue ecosystem. The Clusters use a range:

- *Generic, standard formats* (XML, RDF, JSON, JSON-LD) and protocol standards (OpenAPI);
- *Generic and designed specifically for catalogue exchange* (e.g., OAI-PMH and SWORD).
- *Domain specific examples* that concentrate on API's to support specific formats and reporting guidelines, for example EOOSC-Life's adoption of GA4GH standards for Beacons and the GA4GH [Tool Registry Service](#) technical standard enabling researchers to bring algorithms to datasets, rather than having to move data itself; the EMPHASIS RI [BrAPI](#) plant breeding API, designed to exchange information between plant genotype/phenotype focused applications.
- *Packaging formats* that organise data for import and export between catalogues and repositories: these also fall into generic (BagIt, HDF5, RO-Crate) and specialised (e.g. COMBINE Archive format for systems biology). RO-Crate⁶¹ is a community effort to establish a lightweight approach to packaging research data with their metadata, based on schema.org annotations in JSON-LD. It is being used by the EOOSC-Life cluster to exchange workflows and associated data between registries and between execution platforms. Appendix A lists common data formats and protocols for import/export between data catalogues.

⁶¹ <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/>

4. The RI Clusters

4.1 ENVRI-FAIR

The RI for environmental research brings together 14 environmental and diverse research infrastructures. It plans to implement a ‘hub’, allowing access to metadata for [contributing RIs](#) products through a federated machine-to-machine interface, where the hub would feed directly into the EOSC service catalogue, through the EOSC-hub Marketplace⁶². The cataloguing strategy has been described, and is centred on CERIF (Quimbert *et al.*, 2020) and a flagship federated catalogue proposed, though other documents suggest that the community does not support a single metadata catalogue.

The ENVRI-FAIR approach is documented further in “[Towards Interoperable Research Infrastructures for Environmental and Earth Sciences, LNCS 12003A](#)” (Zhao and Hellström, 2020). Currently the plan is to build on the EPOS⁶³ framework. A deliverable “Design of the service catalogue⁶⁴” reports the preliminary work for drafting the design of the ENVRI-FAIR service catalogue. The work was carried out mostly in the framework of the WP5 “ENVRI catalogue of services” Task Force.

Figure 6: Schematic for ENVRI-FAIR catalogue. Credit Daniele Bailo

In a recent [analysis](#) of Google Dataset Search, the geosciences are highlighted as [particularly successful](#) in making their data [FAIR](#).

⁶² <https://envri.eu/18-months-of-accomplishments/>

⁶³ <https://www.epos-ip.org/>

⁶⁴ <https://envri.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/MS18-WP5-Design-of-the-service-catalogue-1.pdf>

4.2 PaNOSC

The Photon and Neutron Open Science Cloud, brings together 6 RIs and the ExPaNDS partnership of most national photon and neutron sources in Europe. The aim is to develop and provide [services](#) for scientific data, largely through adoption of common metadata standards. The data [catalogue](#) can be searched using a federated search engine through OpenAIRE. The exposure of PaNOSC products to 3rd party catalogues is the task of [WP3](#). PaNOSC is currently engaged, with other partners, in exploring and developing standard vocabulary and dictionaries based on NeXus⁶⁵, a domain-specific metadata schema. Its catalogue stores reference to raw data and the relevant metadata to identify datasets including: proposal information, sample information, experimental parameters, previews, provenance, relationship to derived datasets and relationship to people. The catalogue also aims to facilitate data re-use, sharing and publication via PIDs and DOIs. A Common Portal gives access to Data Analysis Services.

Figure 7: Schematic for PaNOSC cataloguing, Credit Tobias Richter.

4.3 ESCAPE

The European Science Cluster of Astronomy and Particle Physics, brings together 13 partners for harness services and facilities for astronomy, astroparticle & particle physics, into a single EU collaborative cluster. Data at the multi-exabyte level. It exploits the well established astronomical Virtual Observatory framework of astronomical high-level products archive and related services as well as a [ESCAPE Software Repository](#) (the repository of scientific software services) and [ESCAPE Data Infrastructure for Open Science](#) (a scalable federated data infrastructure for open access data service capable of supporting Exabyte-scale data volumes). ESCAPE's metadata catalogue, Virtual Observatory is connected through [B2FIND](#), and provides

⁶⁵ <https://www.nexusformat.org>

metadata around data collections and services (Resource Metadata for the Virtual Observatory⁶⁶), where the harvested sources provide Dublin Core with domain-specific extensions, aligned with DataCite metadata schema, as well as IVOA units and standards⁶⁷.

Figure 8: Schematic for ESCAPE cataloguing, Credit Kay Graf.

4.4 SSHOC

The Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud brings together 6 RIs to provide an open cloud for social sciences and humanities where data, tools, and training are available and accessible for users. The consortium covers the whole data cycle, from data creation and curation, to optimal data reuse, and can address training and advocacy to increase actual reuse of data. A series of interviews revealed that there are in 19+ metadata standards currently used within this community (a modest number compared to EOSC-Life) with a recommendation for adoption of domain-specific standards together with common generic metadata vocabularies to maximise expressivity. Nonetheless, the SSHOC community has a strong alignment around DDI, CIDOC-CRM (and its extensions, especially PEM) and CMDI.

SSHOC is still in the early stages of development, with an Interoperability Hub planned for delivery around Feb 2022⁶⁸. This will consist of a registry of the most relevant metadata formats and accompanying interconversion services, as well as format, software and standards recommendations. SSHOC centres on a ‘[Open Marketplace](#)’ discovery portal, which catalogues tools, services, training materials, datasets and activities for the Social Sciences and Humanities research communities (Barbot *et al.*, 2019).

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https://www.researchgate.net/profile/William_Omullane/publication/234351289_Resource_Metadata_for_the_Virtual_Observatory/links/00b4953c5452d25773000000/Resource-Metadata-for-the-Virtual-Observatory.pdf

67 <https://www.ivoa.net/rdf/>

68 <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/service-catalogue>

Figure 9: Schematic for SHHOC cataloguing, Credit Frank Fischer.

4.5 EOSC-Life

EOSC-Life brings together 13 biological and medical RIs to create an open collaborative space for digital biology. It aims to publish FAIR life science data resources to the cloud, creating an ecosystem of innovative tools in EOSC. The cluster is coordinated by [ELIXIR](#), the European Bioinformatics e-infrastructure coordinating data, resources and services. Like ENVRI, the RIs are diverse, ranging from structures at atomic resolution to population level data, from mouse models to clinical trials, from medicinal chemistry to plant phenotyping to biobanking. A FAIRsharing collection acts as a lightweight catalogue of 100+ data repositories and lists 870+ standards in the life science space. Each data repository might have 1000s of datasets. Each RI retains its own governance over its data repositories and there is no plan to develop a single portal given the radically different data types and use cases. Instead emphasis is placed on (i) links in interfaces, common vocabularies, common minimum cataloguing terms and cross-walks, and shared API standards; and (ii) cross-cutting generic approaches (e.g. using schema.org), generic infrastructure (e.g. Ontology Lookup Service), generic catalogues (e.g. WorkflowHub, bio.tools, biocontainers). ELIXIR has committed to Bioschemas as a lightweight mechanism for metadata exchange and interoperability, and international standards such as GA4GH. The harmonised part of the EOSC-Life infrastructure is for the cross-cutting services for tools, workflows and containers, primarily developed by ELIXIR. This shares a metadata bus of standards (see figure .

Figure 10: Schematic for EOSC-Life cataloguing of tools, workflows and containers Credit Carole Goble.

Tool and Workflow Registries

EOSC-Life has made preliminary recommendations for FAIR repositories and provenance; however, when dealing with EOSC-Life datasets one is really dealing with each participating RI.

[ELIXIR](#) provides cross-cutting registries for identifier resolution ([Identifiers.org](#)) and ontology resolution (Ontology Lookup Service). [OmicsDI](#) is a catalogue of indexed 'omics dataset (storing metadata from datasets) and a [FAIRsharing collection](#) lists the recognized ELIXIR data repositories⁶⁹

[BBMRI-ERIC](#) focuses on biobanking, covering researchers, biobankers, industry, and patients. It offers quality management services, support with ELSI (ethical, legal and societal issues), and provides online tools and software. The '[BBMRI-ERIC Directory](#)' is the world's largest operating biobank catalogue, which provides information on candidate biobanks. BBMRI-ERIC provides a detailed technical [description](#) to contribute to the directory, which includes the data model and the federated process through which directory data is updated through National Node level contributions. The BBMRI-ERIC data model provides an extension to [MIABIS](#) (Minimum Information about Biobank Information Sharing) Core 2.0

[ECRIN-ERIC](#) European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network provides tailored support for the preparation and implementation of multinational clinical trials in Europe. ECRIN provides the Clinical Research Metadata [Repository](#), allowing access to documents and data linked to a clinical research study, and to determine accessibility of those results. This means that the data collected and aggregated is presented in a searchable form, and that there is no use of 'expert input' or a 'quality filter'. The repository also includes protocols, information sheets and consent forms, as well as data management plans and descriptive metadata, etc. The underlying data model is based on 'study' and 'data object', where current child terms of these entities which are currently identified by 'textual' definitions are intended to be replaced with controlled lists of terms (for example 'OrganisationID'). Additionally, 'topics' will be identified using controlled vocabularies from category systems such as ICD10 and ATC, rather than free text, and will be referenced using URIs. The original

⁶⁹ <https://fairsharing.org/collections/?q=ELIXIR>

metadata model (is continually being updated; recent changes from version 3 to version 4 are documented [here](#), to reflect use of the DUO (Data Usage Ontology) classification of biomedical consents, and an emerging EOSC classification of document risk.

[EMBRC](#), European Marine Biological Research Centre, focuses on marine biology and ecology. It provides access to its services through a [service catalogue](#), for which a user must register, then request specific services such as access to organisms (request culture) or experimental facilities, for use in project proposals. EMBRC provides documentation on a [DMP](#) (Data Management Plan), detailing their metadata policies; EMBRC deals with a wide variety of data types, and the DMP details recommended formats and standards (see Appendix A), as well as developing a tool-box of best practice [guidelines](#). Its standards recommendations include EML (Ecological Metadata Language), ISO 19115:2003 - geographic data, [GCMD](#) (Global Change Master Directory).

[EMPHASIS](#) focuses on Plant Phenotyping, providing researchers use of relevant facilities, resources and services. It uses Minimum information standards such as [MIAME](#), [MIAPE](#), [MIAPPE](#), [MSI](#), and MIxS, but additionally makes use of plant-specific extensions of other standards such as [MIAME-Plant](#), [CIMR](#) and the [MIxS](#) plant environment package and vocabularies such as the plant and [crop](#) ontology. There appears to be no central plant phenotypic data catalogue, though BrAPI (described above) seems to be extensively used, as well as the PGP repository, e!DAL and an ontology-driven information system, PHIS. IsaTab in general seems to be used as a practical implementation of the MIAPPE guidelines, with data provided across resources, typically complying with MIAPPE 1.1, and being marked up with schema.org, and provision of various download formats.

[ERINHA](#) focuses on Highly Pathogenic Agents, dedicated to the study of High-consequence pathogens of Risk Group 4 (RG4) by providing the ability to conduct research requiring access to multiple Biosafety Levels (BSL) including BSL4, which are beyond the capability of a single facility. Services must be requested through project submissions, with guidance [provided](#).

[EU-OPENSREEN-ERIC](#) provides access to academic high-throughput screening facilities and medicinal chemistry groups expertise, allowing scientists to carry out screening projects at partner laboratories. It provides access to a compound collection, containing over 100,000 commercial compounds, allowing collecting of extensive information on physico-chemical, cellular toxicity and anti-microbial properties. The European Chemical Biology Database (ECBD) is currently in a pilot phase. and will be a web portal with search and analysis capabilities. A 'pilot' [screening library](#) consists of about 5.000 compounds. The final ECBD will support curation, annotation and organization of data and metadata. Data will be deposited with a flexible privacy model for rapid and safe dissemination and exploitation. Provenance and security will be used for traceability of IP (citable indexing of data points (EUOS, DOI or URL) and will also link back to original lab sources for primary data. There will also be links to SAR (e.g. ChEMBL), Chemical Structure (e.g. PubChem), and Target (e.g. UniProt) resources. Links established with new NIH-funded BARD resource.

While no metadata model seems currently available, a Data Management Plan has been delivered, and related material will be available in due course.

[EURO-BIOIMAGING](#) focuses on biological and biomedical imaging, allowing life scientists to access imaging instruments, expertise, training opportunities and data management services. A number of centralised resources for biological images include the [BioImage Archive](#), the [Image Data Resource \(IDR\)](#) and the [Electron Microscopy Public Image Archive](#). There doesn't seem to be a catalogue.

[INFRAFRONTIER](#) focuses on generating, phenotyping, archiving and distributing model mammalian genomes. It additionally provides access to tools and data for research using mouse models, focusing on the systematic phenotyping of mouse mutants and their subsequent archiving and distribution through the European Mouse Mutant Archive ([EMMA](#)). Strain information within EMMA is supplemented/annotated using external resources: Mouse Genome Informatics ([MGI](#)), International Mouse Phenotype Collaboration ([IMPC](#)), Disease Ontology ([DO](#)), [Ensembl](#), [PubMed](#), [MeSH](#), [Orphanet](#), and the EBI Ontology Lookup Service ([OLS](#)). The strain catalogue itself does not appear to provide any machine readable metadata ([example](#)).

[Instruct-ERIC](#) facilitates access to services and technologies in structural biology, specifically supporting research that uses integrated approaches and technologies. Besides technical services, Instruct-ERIC also provides some support for pilot studies, runs internships and training courses to promote advancements in structural biology technologies and techniques. Instruct-ERIC hosts a service and technology [catalogue](#) providing access to crystallisation or analytic services available through its partner sites, as well as providing listings of its computational [services](#). Unfortunately these lists are not supplemented with metadata, nor use any descriptive vocabularies to allow computational processing.

[ISBE](#), Infrastructure for Systems Biology Europe, aimed to connect national systems biology centres. Systems Biology is inherently a collaborative and cross-disciplinary domain and requires expertise and technologies that cross disciplinary boundaries to be integrated with specific projects. Consequently, ISBE needed to link to various/multiple other ESFRI infrastructures in a meaningful way, for example allowing the creation of computer models which integrate both "omics" data from ELIXIR with quantitative imaging data from Euro-BioImaging. It adopted the [FAIRDOME-SEEK](#) as its cataloguing/repository platform and the [FAIRDOMHub](#), a public open resource hosted in Germany, was sponsored by ISBE. The Hub is an integrated catalogues/archives. This federated approach organises and relates the objects and their roles in an investigation using the [ISA](#) (Investigation, Study, Assay) metadata schema (see figure 4). The approach means that context of an investigation is retained whilst the objects can be deposited in the authoritative repositories of the community or secure behind authentication and authorisation frameworks if they are sensitive. ISBE is being wrapped into the ELIXIR RI; its successor is IBISBA, the new RI for Industrial Biotechnology, which uses the same platform and has established an [IBISBAHub](#).

[MIRRI](#) Microbial Resource Research Infrastructure focuses on microbial biodiversity to exploit knowledge to further bioeconomy and bioscience. It has over 50 public biorepositories and research institutes and provides a collaborative work environment, driving collaboration across borders and disciplines. MIRRI provides a web search interface to access many of its resources, including the search for microbial strains, yeast strains and glossary terms. It also provides collaboratively generated guidelines for culture collections (CC) curators for the inclusion of their collections to MIRRI into the MIRRI Information System (MIRRI-IS), using a defined format. The starting points for this standard largely entailed a comparison to the CABRI data fields, and

comparison to the ISO/AWI 21710 document on “Specification on data management and publication in microbial resource centres”.

[EATRIS-ERIC](#) focuses on translational medicine, for preclinical and early clinical development of vaccines, drugs and diagnostics. It provides access to technologies in translational research, provisioned through a central hub, focused on solutions in the fields of advanced therapy medicinal products, biomarkers, imaging and tracing, small molecules and vaccines. Its portfolio of [services](#) centres on predicting product performance, patient selection, and facilitating entry into clinical development safely and efficiently.

5. Conclusion

Task 4 is focussed on aligning the **research data cataloguing** efforts in the 5 RI Cluster projects and their constituent content providers with the EOSC Portal, and to foster interoperability for discovery, accessibility and reusability of data.

The ultimate objective is to integrate the pre-existing and ongoing RI data catalogues into the [OpenAIRE Research Graph](#), whose APIs will in turn be integrated into the EOSC Portal to provide EOSC scientific product catalogue’s functionality.

We discussed key topics concerning metadata catalogue integration, data cataloguing strategies and common themes from the Cluster projects. The key point is that *one size does not fit all*.

The Clusters are not homogeneous entities. They are made up of multiple and diverse Research Infrastructures that vary in their cataloguing maturity and approaches. Some have Cluster-wide recommendations and governance but others are so diverse that they delegate to their partner RIs. Data catalogues are governed at: the Cluster, the RI, the RI national/institutional member and the individual resources level. A few Clusters have made steps towards defining their recommendations for FAIR catalogues but most have not.

The diversity of Cluster data ranges over: the data types, the granularity of the data (from structures at atomic resolution to population level data), the necessary associated metadata, the complexity of data and relationships between data sets, data scales (boutique small data resources to large enterprise repositories), and the data objects catalogued (software, tools, workflows, teaching materials).

The definition of what a dataset is is not simple. Each RI has its own thoughts. Metadata is often stratified into data catalogue, dataset and data record, which effects the standards used at each layer, the level of “FAIR compliance” that the catalogue can state a claim to, the depth of cross disciplinary catalogue integration and discoverability and the properties that are relevant to EOSC services. *Similar and/or domain agnostic metadata properties* are used to describe data catalogues and datasets across different scientific domains, typically with shallow level of detail; and *domain-specific metadata properties* related to the nature of the entity are described within data records, typically with deeper level of detail.

All clusters are concerned with *common interfaces and community standards* to operate within a federation of catalogues. They recommend common standards for (low-level) interoperability/discoverability and domain-specific standards (for expressivity and deep interoperability/reuse). Catalogue and metadata harmonisation already exists, and is well established within the thematic communities and should be

honoured and respected. Interoperability for its own sake is unproductive and wasteful; the clusters expend effort on interoperability between metadata and their catalogues only where and when it makes sense (through real examples) and brings benefit. The case for arbitrary pan-discipline interoperability of significantly different datatypes is particularly unclear for the Cluster with long-held and diverse RIs - notably EOSC-Life and ENVRI-FAIR- where such interoperability may be worth considering *only* where a tangible Use Case is presented.

The Clusters have a spectrum of maturity for their cataloguing activities, web services, portals, dataset dumps and workflow services. However, all have a **significant legacy** of pre-existing categories, repositories and associated processes with different user groups of data generators, data browsers and downloaders, data analysts, and data owners. EOSC should build on what is already used, not force a new manner of working. There is a need to ensure low barriers to entry for portal submission and discovery with maximum convenience for users and providers. Automation is needed where possible to reduce the human work of cataloguing and curation. All report the need to clarify incentives for opening data and reciprocity for doing so. All integrate knowledge and training with services and data, with most providing some support for software and training catalogues.

Not all data is open. The Clusters have a range of access protocols to the data – embargoes, sensitive data, IPR issues etc – and rules of participation. Closed data has limited exposure of metadata and additional metadata for controlling access.

Cluster level catalogues vs RI level catalogues. Some clusters have attempted a single catalogue (notably SHHOC and PaNOSC). Others (EOSC-Life and ENVRI-FAIR) recognise the heterogeneity and autonomy of their member RIs and seek to overcome the differences through mechanisms other than a single catalogue, through interoperability and federation with standards, APIs and federated custom search (PaNOSC). All are concerned with the long term maintenance and sustainability of cluster level catalogues. Lightweight approaches for cross-walking between catalogues and for FAIR cataloguing are favoured by the Clusters with large numbers of RIs and diverse data (EOSC-Life, ENVRI-FAIR).

The SSHOC uses the term “Marketplace” but others consider that they do not operate in a marketplace for trading digital objects but instead are enabling access to digital objects.

There are a large number of players active in this arena, and a collaborative approach will more likely ensure a more diverse set of adopters of emergent strategy: CODATA, RDA, GOFAIR and especially the FAIRsFAIR project have produced a number of deliverables of relevance, discussed above.

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7. Appendix A: Cataloging Standards

Table A1 - Widely used metadata standards for cataloging (incomplete)

Standard	Description	Remarks
DCAT	A vocabulary designed to facilitate interoperability between data catalogs published on the Web, targeting datasets and data services. Body: W3C	
DCAT2	Improved version of DCAT to address deficiencies, especially with respect to identifiers and data citation issues. Body: W3C	DCAT2 supercedes DCAT, but maintains the DCAT namespace to retain backwards compatibility
Schema.org	A community activity, instigated by major web search engine providers, and which provides, usually, a 'shallow' vocabulary to describe resources on the web. Hierarchical collections of 'types', where each 'type' has defined 'properties'. Properties may be selected for use to define a 'profile'. Body: Schema.org	40% of the web is marked up with schema.org; drives the search engine knowledge graphs and Google Dataset search.
Dublin Core	A set of vocabulary terms that can be used to describe digital or physical resources Body: Dublin Core Metadata Initiative	
PROV	A vocabulary that describes entities, and the activities and people responsible for bringing them into existence. Body: W3C	
ISDIAH	International Standard for Describing Institutions with Archival Holdings, and the ISAD(G): General International Standard Archival Description - Second edition Body: ICA	
CERIF	EU Recommendation to the Member States for research information since 1991 Body: euroCRIS	scholarly outputs, people and organisations, research funders and project/grants, consistent tracking of open-access research publications across scholarly systems.
RIOXX	Developed for institutional repositories to share metadata about the scholarly resources they contain. RIOXX has also proven to be generally useful as a	scholarly outputs, people and organisations, research funders and project/grants,

	standard for sharing metadata between repositories and network services such as large-scale metadata aggregators (e.g. Core).	consistent tracking of open-access research publications across scholarly systems.
	Body: Community group	

Table A2 - Widely used de facto metadata standards

Standard	Description	Remarks
Datacite	An organisation that issues DOIs for research outputs such as publications, as well as for datasets. As such, it is committed to providing alongside those DOIs a set of metadata that complies with its metadata schema, which continues to be refined. Body: DataCite	A commercial enterprise developed without a public consensus
CKAN formats	CKAN is a tool for making open data websites to manage and publish collections of data. It is used by national and local governments, research institutions, and other organizations who collect a lot of data. Body: CKAN	Open community

Table A3 - Examples of data type specific metadata standards used by the Research Infrastructures

Standard	Description	Discipline
ISAAR (CPF)	International Standard Archival Authority Record for Corporate Bodies, Persons and Families, 2nd Edition Body: ICA	
ISDIAH	International Standard for Describing Institutions with Archival Holdings, and the ISAD(G): General International Standard Archival Description - Second edition Body: ICA	
SDMX	Statistical Data and Metadata eXchange (SDMX) Body: Community group	statistical data
EML	EML - Ecological Metadata Language Body: Community group	widespread use in environmental science and earth sciences
ISO 19115	An internationally-adopted schema for describing geographic information and services. It provides information about the identification, the extent, the quality, the spatial and temporal schema, spatial reference, and distribution of digital geographic data.	environmental science and earth sciences

	Body: International Standards Organisation	
CF (Climate and Forecast metadata)	The conventions define metadata that provide a definitive description of what the data in each variable represents, and the spatial and temporal properties of climate and forecast data.	climate change
	Body: grassroots community	
Bioschemas	Developed in the biosciences domain, as a set of specific profiles of Schema.org and typed extensions, targeted to improve the findability of biosciences data exposed through web-based means. Has some traction but still to tip into significant adoption due to tussles with Schema.org governance.	Life sciences and biodiversity, cross-cutting for data catalogue, set & record
	Body: community sponsored by ELIXIR RI.	
Research Schemas	An umbrella effort looking at Schema.org extensions for domain specific material.	wide-ranging
	Body: Research Data Alliance WG	
MIBBI	Minimum Information for Biological and Biomedical Investigations - an umbrella term to cover the large collection of reporting guidelines in life sciences.	life sciences
	Body: none, see FAIRsharing	
METS	Metadata Encoding and Transmission Standard (METS) Body: METS Board in collaboration with the Network Development and MARC Standards Office of the Library of Congress, and started as an initiative of the Digital Library Federation.	digital libraries. cross-cutting
CIDOC CRM	Conceptual Reference Model (CRM) for information integration in the field of cultural heritage. Body: CIDOC	Cultural heritage and museums
CMDI	Component MetaData Infrastructure (CMDI) Body: CLARIN	Languages

Table A4 - Major organisations coordinating or contributing to data type specific data cataloguing standards

Organisation	Description	Discipline
Open Geospatial Consortium	extensive range of free, publicly available geospatial standards	all geospatial sciences
Global Alliance for Genomics and Health	is a policy-framing and technical standards-setting organization, seeking to enable	life sciences

	responsible genomic data sharing within a human rights framework .	
International Virtual Observatory Alliance	Oversees standardization of data and metadata, standardization of data exchange methods, and a registry, which lists available services and what can be done with them. https://fairsharing.org/collection/IVOA	astronomical data
Biodiversity Information Standards (TDWG)	a non-profit organization and community dedicated to developing biodiversity information standards https://fairsharing.org/collection/TDWGBiodiversity	biodiversity, taxonomy
DDI - Data Documentation Initiative	a not for profit creating an international standard for describing data from the social, behavioral, and economic sciences	social, behavioral, and economic sciences
euroCRIS	Manages CERIF: the Common European Research Information Format used by CRIS systems.	research organisations
ICA (International Council on Archives)	Standards for the management of records and the preservation, care and use of the world's archival heritage. Records and archive professionals are the prime stakeholders.	archival heritage
ISO (International Organization for Standardization)	An independent, non-governmental international organization with a membership of 165 national standards bodies. Covers all manner of areas, disciplines and functions. 398 results found for the searchword "metadata".	wide-ranging, from biodiversity and life sciences to food management and quality processes.
Genomics Standards Consortium	The aim of the GSC is making genomic data discoverable. The GSC enables genomic data integration, discovery and comparison through international community-driven standards.	life sciences, genomic data
Research Data Alliance	A community-driven initiative to drive the social and technical infrastructure to enable open sharing and re-use of data. Not officially a standards organisation but makes recommendations or varying importance and quality.	wide-ranging and cross-cutting
CODATA	the Committee on Data of the International Science Council (ISC). Promotes global collaboration to advance Open Science and FAIR.	wide-ranging and cross-cutting
World Data System	Support the International Science Council 's vision by promoting long-term stewardship	natural and social sciences, and the humanities.

	<p>of, and universal and equitable access to, quality-assured scientific data and data services, products, and information. Coordinates and supports trusted scientific data services for the provision, use, and preservation of relevant datasets.</p>	
GO-FAIR	<p>A bottom-up, stakeholder-driven and self-governed initiative that aims to implement the FAIR data principles, through community Implementation Networks (IN).</p> <p>Notable IN include Discovery run by Open Knowledge Maps</p>	wide-ranging and cross-cutting
Open Knowledge Maps	<p>A charitable non-profit organization building a visual interface to increase the visibility of research findings for science and society.</p>	wide-ranging and cross-cutting
IEEE	<p>The Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers is a professional association that also sets standards</p>	wide-ranging and cross-cutting
Open Archives Initiative	<p>Develops and promotes interoperability standards that aim to facilitate the efficient dissemination of content. Has its roots in the open access and institutional repository movements.</p>	Cross-cutting
ANSI/ NISO	<p>The National Information Standards Organization, a non-profit association accredited by the American National Standards Institute (ANSI). Identify, develop, maintain, and publish technical standards and recommended practices to manage information in the digital environment. NISO standards apply to both traditional and new technologies and to information across its whole lifecycle, from creation through documentation, use, repurposing, storage, metadata, and preservation.</p>	largely cross-cutting
W3C The World Wide Web Consortium	<p>Primary activity is to develop protocols and guidelines that ensure long-term growth for the Web. Standards define key parts of what makes the World Wide Web work.</p>	Cross-cutting
National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST)	<p>Part of the U.S. Department of Commerce. Set standards for measurements from the smart electric power grid and electronic health records to atomic clocks, advanced nanomaterials, and computer chips.</p>	Cross-cutting

CIDOC	ICOM International Committee for Documentation	museums and cultural heritage

Table A5 - Common data formats used by repositories and for import/export between data catalogues

Formats	Description	Remarks
The BagIt File Packaging Format (V1.0)	a set of hierarchical file layout conventions for storage and transfer of arbitrary digital content. A "bag" has just enough structure to enclose descriptive metadata "tags" and a file "payload" but does not require knowledge of the payload's internal semantics. This BagIt format is suitable for reliable storage and transfer.	Used by RO-Crate and gaining a lot of popularity
HDF5	A data model, library, and file format for storing and managing data. It supports an unlimited variety of datatypes, and is designed for flexible and efficient I/O and for high volume and complex data.	
RO-Crate	A community effort to establish a lightweight approach to packaging research data with their metadata. It is based on schema.org annotations in JSON-LD, and aims to make best-practice in formal metadata description accessible and practical for use in a wider variety of situations, from an individual researcher working with a folder of data, to large data-intensive computational research environments.	Sponsored by digital library and EOSC-Life/NIH use cases, but cross cutting
Oxford Common File Layout	Describes an application-independent approach to the storage of digital information in a structured, transparent, and predictable manner. It is designed to promote long-term object management best practices within digital repositories.	
OAI-ORE	Open Archives Initiative Object Exchange and Reuse, defines standards for the description and exchange of aggregations of Web resources. These aggregations (compound digital objects), may combine distributed resources with multiple media types including text, images, data, and video.	Widely used in the library and OR community.
Exchange Protocols		
ResourceSync	ANSI/NISO Z39.99-2017, Open Archives Initiative ResourceSync Framework Specification, describes a synchronization framework for the web consisting of various capabilities that allow third-party systems to remain synchronized with a server's evolving resources.	

OAI-PMH	The Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting, provides an application-independent interoperability framework based on <i>metadata harvesting</i> . <i>Data Providers</i> administer systems that support the OAI-PMH as a means of exposing metadata; and <i>Service Providers</i> use metadata harvested via the OAI-PMH as a basis for building value-added services.	Widely used in the library and OR community.
SWORD 3.0	A protocol enabling clients and servers to communicate around complex digital objects, especially with regard to supporting the deposit of these objects into a service like a digital repository. Complex digital objects consist of both Metadata and File content, where the Files may be in a variety of formats, there may be many files, and some may be very large. The protocol defines semantics for creating, appending, replacing, deleting, and retrieving information about these complex resources. It also enables servers to communicate regarding the status of treatment of deposited content, such as exposing ingest workflow information.	
DCAT(2) and DCAT(3) forthcoming	An RDF vocabulary designed to facilitate interoperability between metadata catalogues published on the Web. Sponsored by the W3C.	Cross cutting and widespread

Table A6: Mapping of classes from DCAT to Schema.org, including obligation (Obl.) status (M, mandatory; R recommended; O, optional). Modified from <https://ec-irc.github.io/dcat-ap-to-schema-org/>.

DCAT-AP				Schema.org
Specification	Obl.	Label	QName	
[DCAT-AP]	M	Agent	foaf:Agent	schema:Organization schema:Person
[DCAT-AP]	M	Catalogue	dcat:Catalog	schema:DataCatalog
[DCAT-AP]	M	Dataset	dcat:Dataset	schema:Dataset
[DCAT-AP]	R	Category	skos:Concept	schema:Thing
[DCAT-AP]	R	Category Scheme	skos:ConceptScheme	schema:Enumeration
[DCAT-AP]	R	Distribution	dcat:Distribution	schema:DataDownload
[DCAT-AP]	R	Licence Document	dct:LicenseDocument	schema:CreativeWork schema:URL

D4.3 Analysis of existing research data cataloguing efforts towards integrated discovery

[DCAT-AP]	0	Catalogue Record	dcat:CatalogRecord	schema:ListItem
[DCAT-AP]	0	Checksum	spdx:Checksum	schema:Thing
[DCAT-AP]	0	Document	foaf:Document	schema:CreativeWork schema:URL
[DCAT-AP]	0	Identifier	adms:Identifier	schema:PropertyValue
[DCAT-AP]	0	Kind	vcard:Kind	schema:ContactPoint
[DCAT-AP]	0	Location	dct:Location	schema:Place
[DCAT-AP]	0	Media Type or Extent	dct:MediaTypeOrExtent	schema:Text schema:URL
[DCAT-AP]	0	Period of Time	dct:PeriodOfTime	schema:DateTime
[DCAT-AP]	0	Provenance Statement	dct:ProvenanceStatement	schema:CreativeWork schema:URL
[GeoDCAT-AP]	0	Reference System	dct:Standard	schema:CreativeWork schema:URL
[DCAT-AP]	0	Rights Statement	dct:RightsStatement	schema:CreativeWork schema:URL
[GeoDCAT-AP]	0	Service	dctype:Service	schema:Service
[DCAT-AP]	0	Standard	dct:Standard	schema:CreativeWork schema:URL

More extensive crosswalks across metadata schema (such as DataCite, DCAT2, EDM1, DATS) can be found through the Research Schemas Working Group⁷⁰.

Table A7 - EDM1 Properties - from <https://eosc-edmi.github.io/properties>

Property	Description	Minimum Functional	Minimum Operational	Recommended Functional	Recommended Operational	Optional Functional	Optional Operational	RDA Metadata guideline
name	A descriptive name for the dataset	X						None
description	A short summary describing a dataset	X						Description

⁷⁰ <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1P6WH8h4OnIVR9UJj3FcOebNUplnKNBCuvEp3NsLRho4/edit#gid=0>

D4.3 Analysis of existing research data cataloguing efforts towards integrated discovery

identifier	<i>The identifier property represents any kind of identifier for any kind of dataset</i>	X						Unique Identifier
url	<i>The location of a page describing the dataset</i>	X			X			Location (URL)
creator	<i>The creator/author of this dataset</i>	X			X			Originator
dateCreated	<i>The date on which the dataset was created</i>	X					X	Temporal coordinates
license	<i>A license under which the dataset is distributed</i>		X	X				Availability
dataStandard	<i>The standard in which the content of the dataset is represented</i>		X	X				None
dateModified	<i>The date on which the dataset was most recently modified</i>		X					None
accessUrl	<i>The link to download the dataset</i>		X					None
accessInterface	<i>The type of interface to present the dataset</i>		X					None
structure	<i>The description of the structure of the dataset</i>				X			Schema

D4.3 Analysis of existing research data cataloguing efforts towards integrated discovery

includedIn	<i>A dataset or data catalog which contains the dataset</i>			X	X			None
measurementTechnique	<i>A technique or technology used in a dataset corresponding to the method used for measuring the corresponding variables</i>			X				None
keywords	<i>Keywords or tags used to describe the dataset</i>			X				Keywords
variablesMeasured	<i>The variables that are measured in the dataset</i>			X				None
format	<i>The format in which the content of the dataset is encoded to present the information, typically a MIME format</i>				X			Medium / Format
scientificType	<i>Scientific domain or type of the information provided in the dataset</i>				X			None
includes	<i>A dataset or data catalog contained in the dataset</i>				X			None
contentType	<i>Type of content provided in the dataset based on its origin and type of processes (raw, processed, summarised)</i>				X			None

D4.3 Analysis of existing research data cataloguing efforts towards integrated discovery

size	<i>Size of the dataset using a digital information multiple unit byte symbol (MB, GB, PT, ...)</i>				X			None
authentications	<i>Type of authentication required to access the dataset</i>				X			None
version	<i>The version of the dataset</i>					X	X	None
metric	<i>Metric to provide some quantitative or qualitative information about the dataset</i>					X	X	None
sameAs	<i>Other URLs that can be used to access the dataset page</i>					X		None
spatialCoverage	<i>The location depicted or described in the content</i>					X		Spatial coordinates
temporalCoverage	<i>The property indicates the period that the content applies to</i>					X		None
citation	<i>A citation or reference to another work that describes the dataset</i>					X		Citations
referenceCitation	<i>A citation or reference to that describes the dataset</i>						X	Related publications
compression	<i>Type of compression used in the dataset</i>						X	None

D4.3 Analysis of existing research data cataloguing efforts towards integrated discovery

<i>authorisation</i>	<i>Type of authorisation required to access the dataset</i>						X	<i>None</i>
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